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D 2.3

Innovative Teaching Concept on Standardisation- Use Guide for Standardisation Education

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D2.3 – Innovative Teaching Concept on Standardisation – Use Guide for Standardisation Education

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Lead author	Ivana Mijatovic (UB)
Contributors	Knut Blind (FHG) Rudi Bekkers (TU/e) Geerten van de Kaa (TUD) Nizar Abdelkafi (POLIMI) Paul Wiegmann (TU/e) Maitane Olabarria Uzquiano (SBS) Biljana Tomic (UB) Magnus Hakvag (HoK) Hristina Veljanova (UG) Jonas Gamalielsson (SKO) Björn Lundell (SKO) Hugo Alexer Parada Gelvez (PM)
Peer reviewers	Geerten van de Kaa (TUD) Nizar Abdelkafi (POLIMI) Knut Blind (FHG)
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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AFNOR	Association Française de Normalisation
ANSI	American National Standards Institute
APEC	Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation
API	American Petroleum Institute
ASME	American Society of Mechanical Engineers
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
BIPM	Bureau of Weights and Measures
BSI	British Standards Institute
CEDEFOP	European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
CWA	CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreement
DIN	Deutsches Institut für Normung
EC	European Commission
EN	European Standard
ESO	European Standards Organization
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standards Institute
EQF	European Qualifications Framework
EU	European Union
FRAND	Fair, Reasonable, and Non-Discriminatory
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IAF	International Accreditation Forum
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
ILAC	International Laboratory Accreditation Cooperation
ILO	Intended Learning Outcome
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IS	International Standard
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
ISO	International Organization for Standardisation
ITA	Industry Technical Agreement
ITCoS	Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
IWA	International Workshop Agreement
KA	Knowledge Area
KM	Knowledge Management
MSS	Management System Standard
NAFP	National Accreditation Focal Points
NQI	National Quality Infrastructure
NSB	National Standards Body
OASIS	Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards
PAS	Publicly Available Specification
PC	Project Committee

PTB	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt
QI	Quality Infrastructure
RAND	Reasonable, and Non-Discriminatory
RAB	Regional Accreditation Body
RMO	Regional Metrology Organization
SC	Sub-committee
SEP	Standard Essential Patent
SIG	Special Interest Group
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SDO	Standard Development Organization
SSO	Standards Setting Organization
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise
TBT	Technical Barriers to Trade
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
TTA	Technology Trend Assessment
UN	United Nations
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WG	Working Groups
WTO	World Trade Organization

Keywords

Education, Standardisation, Teaching Concept, Knowledge Areas, EDU4standards.eu

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Executive summary

This document explains the Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS), outlining the features defined in the project proposal for EDU4standards.eu and the General Agreement associated with it. The ITCoS aims to integrate standardisation more comprehensively into the curricula of higher education institutions (HEIs) across Europe. Its purpose is to equip the next generation of professionals with a deep understanding of standardisation, enabling them to contribute effectively to global market dynamics through informed standardisation practices. The ITCoS serves as the foundation for further pilot development, covering courses for bachelor's and master's programs, in-company training, and extra-curricular formats.

The primary target groups for the ITCoS are educators at HEIs (bachelor's and master's levels), vocational school teachers, trainers and educators at National Standardisation Bodies (NSBs), and other organizations that aim to provide high-quality education and training in standardisation. The indirect target group consists of students at the bachelor's and master's levels.

The ITCoS is a multidimensional approach designed to effectively guide the development of new educational curricula (or parts of them) and content while benchmarking existing ones. It aims to support versatile, attractive, and high-quality standardisation education, establishing itself as the most comprehensive and effective approach in this field. The ITCoS is structured around four Knowledge Areas (KA):

1. KA1: Basic Knowledge of Standardisation Needed to Raise Awareness

This area focuses on systematizing fundamental knowledge and skills related to standardisation. It includes organizing topics, existing teaching materials, and best practices from educators. It emphasizes building foundational understanding.

2. KA2: Standardisation Interdependencies with other areas and Roles in Specific Contexts

This area explores the interdependencies and roles of standardisation in various contexts, such as regulatory frameworks, innovation, and markets. It covers overlapping topics and presents different perspectives.

3. KA3: Strategic Use of Standards

This area addresses the general and specific use of standards, focusing on topics such as the implications and impacts of standards implementation, motives and barriers to their adoption, and the skills required to identify the appropriate standard.

4. KA4: Strategic Participation in Standards Development

This area covers the implications and impacts of participating in standards development. It includes skills for engaging in Technical Committees (TCs) and Working Groups (WGs), as well as identifying the need for new standards.

Standardisation is a practical and dynamic discipline. Without practical application, the ITCoS would remain merely a theoretical concept. To ensure its implementation, the ITCoS will serve as the foundation for developing the EDU4standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool, a web-based platform. The initial content of the EDU4standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool, based on the ITCoS, are defined in Appendix 1. This platform will enable continuous improvement of the ITCoS and facilitate the sharing of ideas and content more broadly.

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Introduction

Strong standardisation skills across industry and academia are prerequisites for the success of European actors in standardisation at the international level, which is crucial for Europe's competitiveness, technological sovereignty, ability to reduce dependencies, and protection of European Union (EU) values, including its social and environmental ambitions (EC, 2022d). According to the EU Standardisation Strategy (EC, 2022d), Europe needs the best standardisation experts to successfully pursue its global ambitions and support a digital, green, and resilient single market. A significant impetus to broaden standardisation awareness and knowledge, and to cultivate the next generation of standardisation experts, lies in the development of dedicated standardisation modules within business, law, or engineering degrees (EC, 2022d). Furthermore, the *Commission Recommendation on a Code of Practice on Standardisation in the European Research Area* (EC, 2023c) suggests that standardisation should also be included as a topic in relevant business, innovation, entrepreneurship, technology, and science programs, such as innovation management education.

The **Edu4standards.eu** research project, funded by the EU, aims to engage leading Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) across the EU in standardisation education. The project also seeks to develop an innovative teaching concept of standardisation, which can be applied flexibly in different HEIs. This document outlines the **Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS)** developed by Edu4standards.eu and connects it to two related documents: D2.1 (*Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) for Standardisation Education*) and D2.2 (*Topical and Methodological Map of Standardisation Education*).

The document is structured as follows. Chapter 1 explains the rationale behind the ITCoS of Edu4standards. It details the requirements for ITCoS, describes the challenges and characteristics of the target audiences, and discusses the Humboldtian idea. Additionally, it elaborates on the societal expectations (European sustainable competitiveness and the green and digital transitions aligned with the EU's values) and the industry's need for standardisation education. The role of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) is also carefully examined. Chapter 2 presents the hierarchical model of Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) in line with industry needs, emphasizing how these ILOs can be implemented in HEIs and ensuring the general applicability of topics.

Chapter 3 defines ITCoS as a multidimensional approach designed to effectively guide the development of new educational curricula (or their components). It introduces four knowledge areas that systematize knowledge and skills related to standardisation, as well as associated topics, existing teaching materials, and experiences. The **Edu4standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool** is also introduced in this chapter, with further explanations provided in Appendix 1. Chapter 4 identifies priorities and highlights gaps in knowledge needed for standardisation education. Chapter 5 outlines the conclusions and next steps. Appendix 1 provides an overview of the content of the Edu4standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool tool with topics that have been defined so far and suggested topics for which content has yet to be developed. Appendix 2 shows the ILOs from deliverable D2.1 for the bachelor and master levels.

1. The Rationale behind the Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS) of Edu4standards.eu

1.1. Task T2.3 – Producing the Innovative Teaching Concept

The leading Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) in the European Union (EU) in standardisation education, forming the Edu4standard.eu consortium, have tasks to develop the Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS) with the following features:

- › can be applied flexibly in different HEI (following the Humboldtian idea, see 1.3) and thematic contexts reflecting the needs of industry, including SMEs, explicitly.
- › should be attractive and engaging to the educators in HEI not active yet in providing courses about standardisation and adequate for broad dissemination.
- › will be applied in pilots covering courses for bachelor's, master's, and in-company training; extra-curricular formats (e.g., seasonal school).
- › aimed at integrating standardisation more comprehensively into the curricula of HEIs across Europe, aiming to equip the next generation of professionals with a thorough understanding of standardisation, enabling them to contribute effectively to global market dynamics through informed standardisation practices.
- › intends to cover the broad scope of standardisation, touching on its technical, economic, legal, and societal implications. It will be designed to align with industrial and societal expectations, focusing on supporting sustainable standardisation efforts that adhere to the EU's values.
- › highlights the role of standardisation in facilitating innovation, sustainability, and competitiveness, particularly in the context of the green and digital transitions.

Task T 2.3 will produce:

- › a hierarchical model of Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) in accordance with competencies and skills needed by the industry,
- › define a generic teaching concept use guide for standardisation education for different teaching venues and professional engagement, and
- › define priorities for addressing the gaps in knowledge needed for standardisation education.

1.2. Target Audience

The main target groups for the ITCoS are teachers at HEIs, bachelor and master levels, vocational school teachers, trainers and educators at National Standards Bodies (NSBs), and other organizations that want to provide high-quality education and/or training on standardisation. Indirect target groups are students at the bachelor and master level. However, the concept is versatile and can be accustomed to specific teaching or training contexts (e.g., in-company training) with a certain limitation.

1.2.1. Academic point of view – It is hard to sell a standardisation course

The ITCoS aims to support teachers in including standardisation in their existing courses and motivate them to develop new courses with standardisation content. Reflecting European educational traditions (De Vries, 2011), incorporating the new content and courses into university curricula is based on different state education systems and program accreditations (national and professional); thus, support from HEI management and colleagues is needed. Substantial effort is required to persuade colleagues of the importance and necessity of the new topic. Incorporating new courses into existing programs differs among HEIs, even within the same country. Institutional support is needed; however, raising awareness of the strategic importance of standardisation among decision-makers and HEI management is an inevitable step toward more education on standardisation. Even with institutional and governmental support, nothing will be changed without knowledgeable and motivated teachers who will create parts of the curricula on standardisation. The ITCoS is focused on raising awareness of standardisation among teachers and building university teachers' capacities to provide high-quality education on standardisation.

All higher education teachers are tasked with continuously improving existing courses and programs, taking evaluations into account to assess success before implementing further enhancements. The majority of university courses are elective, and if there is no student interest in a course, it typically needs to be replaced. In the context of education on standardisation, students' awareness of the importance of gaining knowledge about standardisation is notably limited (Blind, 2018). One challenge is that students often perceive standardisation as a dull subject, leading them to choose other elective courses. At the same time, educators may hesitate to teach standardisation due to a lack of understanding of its significance and unfamiliarity with key issues, which results in prioritizing topics that seem more appealing to students. Teachers may also avoid standardisation because the curriculum is already overloaded with other material (De Vries, 2011). There is a general need to promote the visibility of standardisation as a subject for research and teaching. Furthermore, the industry needs to articulate and communicate the demand for educated employees in the field of standardisation more clearly (Blind, 2019).

Education on standardisation often needs a certain level of multidisciplinary, i.e. requiring the contributions from different disciplines in addition to its relevance for different disciplines (Blind, 2019), and it can be challenging to teach standardisation within one discipline (e.g. economic or legal aspects of one standard in engineering course). Furthermore, for better synergy, it could be wise to connect the initiative on education on standardisation with other initiatives, e.g. for education on sustainability, IPR or entrepreneurship (Catalani et al., 2022). Many already established support initiatives and programs for developing and establishing university curricula about entrepreneurship should incorporate standardisation in addition to the topics of intellectual property (Blind, 2019).

According to Hesser & De Vries's EURAS White Paper (2011), more than 80 European academic entities were active in education on standardisation, and approximately 70% of the entities mentioned above represent universities, business schools and technological educational institutes. The number of HEIs that have included content related to standardisation in their courses and programs is difficult to estimate at present; programs and curricula are constantly changing, but it is evident that there are significant experiences in education on standardisation. Sharing experiences with teaching and learning standardisation can be meaningful and inspiring for newcomers. In conclusion, different actors should support the intentions to teach more about standardisation in many ways; however, collegial support might be "a game changer".

1.2.2. Students – Toward Generation Alpha

Student cohorts are becoming increasingly diverse in their needs, requiring HEI managers and teachers to continuously refine their strategies to maintain high-quality education and provide engaging support for new generations. While we anticipate Generation Alpha's arrival (those born after 2010), Generation Z has already introduced significant changes to higher education and employment.

Generation Z, true digital natives, is a generation that values flexible working hours and adapts relatively easily to innovative work models, even those with no prior precedent, such as the gig economy. These tendencies are reflected in the attitudes of today's university students, particularly those shaped by the post-Covid era. Considering the unique traits of Generation Z learners and post-Covid generation of students, teaching about standards and standardisation should incorporate the following approaches (Mijatović, 2020):

1. **As engaging as possible.** Generation Z students should be encouraged to question and debate instead of relying solely on examples and success stories related to standards and standardisation. Their developed ability to learn independently (Seemiller and Grace, 2017) makes reading assignments more effective when followed by interactive class discussions. Provoking diverse opinions helps maintain their engagement and deepens understanding.
2. **Real-world oriented.** Generation Z prefers meaningful activities and practical problem-solving. They should be challenged with real-world problems that foster their involvement and application of knowledge. Incorporating more real-world scenarios and practices related to standards and standardisation into the curriculum is essential to meet their expectations.
3. **They are interested in global challenges.** Compared to Millennials, Generation Z shows a greater interest in addressing social and global challenges (e.g., climate changes, green transition, etc.). Therefore, independent research and relevant teaching case studies highlighting the global impacts of standards and standardisation are crucial to capture their interest and broaden their perspective.

Predicting the characteristics of future student generations remains a challenge. However, there is an increasing need to integrate technology into education better, not ignoring social media and artificial intelligence (AI), which play controversial roles in shaping an educational ideal that emphasizes holistic personal development. Focusing on how students interpret and process information is critical, rather than simply retrieving it. Seemiller and Grace (2017) state that “future classrooms will incorporate visual, auditory, and kinaesthetic tools to engage students more effectively” (Seemiller and Grace, 2017). Such environments will allow learners to co-create knowledge through collaboration and critical thinking, fostering a more interactive and creative learning space rather than a passive one.

1.3. Following the Humboldtian Idea

Universities have three interconnected missions: teaching, researching, and transferring knowledge to society (Montesinos et al., 2008). In Europe, most universities are research-oriented, where teaching and research are closely linked. The Humboldtian model of higher education advocates for academic freedom, self-governance, and the integration of research and teaching (Table 1) (Bongaerts, 2022). Although Humboldt was not the first to define the principles of the modern research university, his ideas still capture their essence (Backhaus, 2015). He argued that the university's role is to teach students critical thinking

through integrating research and teaching, with the primary goal of advancing knowledge. Research enhances the quality of education, and universities must maintain academic freedom from external pressures. Humboldt viewed science as an ever-evolving field of knowledge, transforming universities from institutions focused on passing down established knowledge to those committed to continuously pursuing discovery (Muller, 1985). He saw universities as spaces for logical and critical thinking and knowledge transmission (Montesinos et al., 2008). Lastly, Humboldt emphasized the difference between school teachers and university professors – while teachers instruct, professors collaborate with students to pursue research/scientific inquiry (Backhaus, 2015).

Learners (Students)	Teachers	Educational System
Individual learning in the centre	Enabling academic studies and not teaching merely to professional skill development	Academic freedom
Reasoning capability	Research for the sake of science and not for society or economic motivations	Unity of education and research
Free choice of educational opportunities	Integration of students in research projects	<i>Bildung</i> ¹ , instead of professional skills training
Individual personality development	Enabling personality and student development as humans through scientific practice	It does not focus on employability
Free interaction with other educated persons	Continuous interaction and communication within the university	Integration of education and research
Communication as a tool of interaction	Protecting freedom of education and freedom of research	Unity of science and presence of all academic disciplines
Language skills for communication		Independence from any state intervention, even if depending on state funding
World citizen		Self-governed institution

Table 1. Key Characteristics of the Humboldtian Model of Higher Education

(Source: Bongaerts, J. C. 2022)

Two interconnected concepts – the Third Mission and the Triple Helix – highlight the role of universities concerning society, industry, and governance. While interpretations of the Third Mission vary across contexts (Jaeger & Kopper, 2014), the concept can encompass all activities outside the academic sphere, fostering interaction with stakeholders, particularly in life-long learning, technology transfer, and innovation (Pausits, 2015). The Third Mission can be defined across three key dimensions: social third mission (services to society without an economic benefit); enterprising third mission (e.g., activities related to technology transfer, patents, consulting for industry and governments, advisory services, and entrepreneurial

¹ Bildung is a German term that encompasses education, personal growth, character development, and emotional and moral maturity. It involves two types of knowledge: one that is easily transferable, such as academic or practical knowledge, which allows for continuous learning and broadening of horizons (horizontal knowledge). The other is knowledge gained through life experiences, emotional depth, and moral development, which is much harder to transfer (vertical knowledge) (see more at the following link: <https://www.nordicbildung.org/lexicon/what-is-bildung/>).

networking) and innovative third mission (e.g., collaborations for patent exploitation, joint ventures with industries, and research aimed at innovation in specific sectors) (Montesinos et al., 2008). The Triple Helix concept emphasizes universities' role in the knowledge society through their interaction with industry and government. Universities play a critical role in fostering networks formed between universities, industry, and government rather than through isolated efforts (Etzkowitz, 2003).

1.4. The Needs for Education on Standardisation

1.4.1. Education on Standardisation for the European Sustainable Competitiveness

Technological change is accelerating rapidly, and there is a need for growth and higher competitiveness, especially in emerging technologies. Prosperity in a sustainable environment while supporting the European social model is extremely difficult without leading in new technologies and effective innovation commercialization. One of the obstacles is the lack of standards and interoperability in specific areas and the lack of coordination of standards (EC, 2024a). The European Commission (EC) states that “scale, standardisation and collaboration will be crucial for EU manufacturers to become competitive” (EC, 2024a). The European Standardisation Strategy (EC, 2022a) also underlines the importance of promoting academic awareness of standardisation.

The paradox is that standardisation's economic importance is undisputed at both the macro and the micro level (Blind, 2019), yet education on standardisation in Europe is not getting as much importance and is still lagging behind Asian countries. To strengthen European competitiveness, high-quality education and training on standardisation are of strategic significance.

1.4.2. Education on Standardisation for the Green and Digital Transition

Education, training, and life-long learning are of the highest importance to the EU. The first guiding principle of the European Pillar of Social Rights for a strong social Europe reads: *Everyone has the right to quality and inclusive education, training and life-long learning to maintain and acquire skills that enable them to participate fully in society and manage successfully transitions in the labour market* (EC, 2024b).

According to the Council Recommendation on Learning for the Green Transition and Sustainable Development (2022/C 243/01), the European Green Deal, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, UNESCO's Strategy for Education for Sustainable Development for 2030, and related work by the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) emphasize the critical role of higher education, and other educational institutions in fostering engagement for driving the necessary changes for a fair, inclusive, and successful green transition (EC, 2022b). The recommendation also highlights the importance of teaching and learning about the green transition and sustainable development through interdisciplinary approaches. It underscores the need to address the socio-emotional dimensions of learning, enabling all learners to become agents of change who can reflect and act, both individually and collectively, at local and global levels, toward creating a more sustainable world.

The role of education is crucial in both the green and digital transitions and their capacity to reinforce one another (known as "twinning"), which will have significant consequences for our future. The *Strategic Foresight Report 2022 on 'Twinning the Green and Digital Transition in the New Geopolitical Context'* offers

a forward-looking and comprehensive view of how these twin transitions will evolve by 2050, identifying key areas for action. Among these critical areas is the need to adapt education and training systems to match the rapidly changing technological and socio-economic landscape and strengthen a global standard-setting approach. This will allow the EU to capitalize on its first-mover advantage in competitive sustainability (EC, 2022c).

The role of standardisation in green and digital transition is marked as highly important. Without standards and standardisation, green and digital transitions would not be possible. In other words, standards and standardisation are a pre-condition for green and digital transition. Additionally, developing and implementing appropriate standards should ensure the interoperability of various technologies, minimize market entry barriers and prevent technologies from becoming obsolete before the end of their lifecycle (Muench et al., 2022). Education and training are needed to equip the workforce with the necessary skills to manage green and digital technologies and ensure sufficient experts are available to drive innovation (Muench et al., 2022).

1.4.3. Education on Standardisation in line with the European Union's values and interests

The European dimension of teaching is based on encouraging a deeper understanding of the European context, common heritage and values and an awareness of the unity and diversity, social, cultural and historical, of the EU and the Member States of the EU (EC, 2018).

D2.1 Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) for Standardisation Education focuses on developing a human-centred intended learning outcomes framework for standardisation education, integrating European core values and interests (green, digital and gender) into standardisation curricula. The framework builds on several pillars:

- › existing work on standardisation,
- › the European Qualifications Framework (EQF), the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) and Bloom's Taxonomy,
- › Article 2 of the Treaty on European Union, where the values upon which the EU is founded, human dignity, freedom, equality, democracy and the rule of law, are outlined and
- › CEDEFOP materials (the European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training).

The EDU4Standards.eu ILOs framework should assist lecturers on standardisation in designing their standardisation courses in line with European values and interests. At the same time, the framework can be used by other stakeholders such as standardisation bodies, industry, NGOs, research organizations, SMEs and citizens. Document D2.1 explains a more profound rationale for the ILOs based on the EU values (Veljanova et a. 2024).

1.4.4. The Industry Needs for Education on Standardisation

1.4.4.1. Industry and Market Needs for Education on Standardisation

Based on empirical research of industry requirements, two documents were considered, the results of which indicate standardisation-related competencies. The first document, titled *European Market Needs for Education in Standardisation/Standardisation-related Competence* (Blind & Drechsler, 2017), presents 14 essential competencies. The second document, IWA 30-1 (ISO, 2019a) and IWA 30-2 (ISO, 2019b) presents the tasks and competencies (knowledge, skills, and personal qualities) necessary for

standardisation professionals' work in companies and standardisation organizations. A comparative view of the competence from the three publications is listed in Table 2.

Industry and Market Needs for Education on Standardisation (company perspective)			
Industry needs (Blind & Drechsler, 2017)	Competence (knowledge, skills and attributes) of standards professionals in companies (IWA 30-1)	Competence (knowledge, skills and attributes) of standards professionals in standards-related organizations (IWA 30-2)	Knowledge Areas (KA)
To know the basic terms used in standards and standardisation			KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness
To know the standardisation institutions. To be able to search for and select appropriate standardisation organizations. To be able to judge which form of standardisation (formal vs. consortia) is appropriate	Knowledge of international standardisation activities and related organizations	Knowledge of international standardisation activities and organizations	
To know the standardisation institutions' processes.	Knowledge of the process and procedure for standards development	Knowledge of the principles, processes and procedures for standards development	
To know the history of standardisation.			
To be able to understand the interactions between standards and the regulatory framework		Knowledge of the laws and systems related to standardisation Knowledge of legislation process and methods	
To be able to understand standardisation in the context of the national quality infrastructure and the macroeconomic environment	Knowledge of requirements and process for certification Knowledge of conformity assessment (testing, inspection, certification) Knowledge of legal, industrial and scientific metrology		KA2. Standardisation interdependencies and roles in specific contexts

Company standardisation	Knowledge of the company standardisation principles*		
	Knowledge of the process and methods to establish a standardisation plan*		
	Knowledge of the company standardisation system*		
	Knowledge of the drafting rules for company standards*		
To be able to understand the impact of implementing standards	Knowledge of the process and methods for an impact analysis of standard application	Knowledge of the validation methods for standards	KA3. Strategic use of standards
	Knowledge of the validation methods for company standards*		
To be able to search for and select appropriate standards	Knowledge of existing standards/technical regulations in a specified sector	Knowledge of existing standards/technical regulations in a specified sector	
	Knowledge of external standards related to products and technology		
To be able to implement standards in product or process development			
To be able to understand the impact of standardisation processes			
To be able to identify the need for standards			
To be able to identify the need for getting involved in standardisation	Knowledge of methodologies/ methods for strategy development	Knowledge of methodologies/ methods for strategy development	KA4. Strategic participation in standards development
	Knowledge of methodologies for performance management	Knowledge of methodologies for performance management	
	Knowledge of standard/technology analysis and needs analysis	Knowledge of methods for standard/technology analysis and needs survey	
To be able to propose		Knowledge of the	

new work items in standardisation		drafting rules for standards	
To be able to strategically influence the agenda in standardisation processes		Knowledge of standards application to the development of technical regulations	
		Knowledge of responding to foreign technical regulations (WTO/TBT)	
To be able to be passively involved in standardisation processes (observer)			
To be able to be actively involved in standardisation processes (participant)		Knowledge of program management	
		Knowledge of harmonization with International Standards	
		Knowledge of project management	

Table 2. Definition of Knowledge Areas for the ITCoS based on Industry Needs/Competencies in Standardisation

Some competencies may be found in IWA 30-1 and IWA 30-2, but not in the study by Blind and Drechsler (2017). The IWA 30:1-2019 also lists *Technical knowledge in a specific sector* and *Knowledge of statistical methods*. The IWA 30-2:2019 also lists *Technical knowledge in a particular sector*, *Knowledge of marketing and public relations*, *Knowledge of IT systems and database management*, *Knowledge of human resource development* and *Knowledge of statistical methods*. All mentioned skills and competencies are hard skills, which is why these need to be complemented by specific soft skills, e.g., negotiation, diplomacy, networking, communication, teamwork, self-responsibility, etc.

All identified industry needs/competencies in standardisation (Table 2) are classified into four Knowledge Areas (KAs):

- › KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness.
- › KA2. Standardisation interdependencies and roles in specific contexts (interdependencies with adjacent/other areas)
- › KA3. Strategic use of standards
- › KA4. Strategic participation in standards development

1.4.4.2. *Education in supporting Sustainable Standardisation efforts in SMEs²*

Formal and non-formal education is essential in supporting Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in understanding and using standards, especially in transitioning to more sustainable business models and facilitating their active participation in the standards development process. Education is crucial in helping SMEs adopt and implement standards that promote long-term environmental, economic, and social sustainability. From the SME perspective, graduates entering the workforce should possess a blend of theoretical understanding and practical skills that enable them to leverage standards as strategic tools. This enhances operational efficiency and supports innovation, compliance, and sustainability – key drivers of success in competitive markets.

Therefore, targeted educational initiatives, especially teaching the basics of standards, are essential to raise awareness about the importance of standards, how to implement them effectively, and how to get involved in their development. SMEs would expect students to have a solid foundational knowledge of standards relevant to their industry. This includes understanding the types of standards (national, European, and international standards), their development processes, and their role in supporting regulatory compliance and market access. Graduates should be able to identify which standards apply to different aspects of a business, from product design and safety to quality management and environmental practices. This knowledge ensures that SMEs can quickly adapt to legal and market requirements, reducing non-compliance risk.

A practical and interactive approach that combines technical knowledge with real-world examples is therefore essential from the perspective of SMEs to learn about standards (e.g., how to find them, how to read them, how to use them) through scenarios tailored to their business needs, while ensuring simplicity and clarity for better understanding. Beyond theory, graduates must demonstrate the ability to apply standards pragmatically within the SME environment. This includes interpreting complex documentation, integrating standards into daily operations, and using them to streamline processes. SMEs benefit from employees who can translate standards into actionable steps, ensuring products and services meet quality benchmarks without incurring unnecessary costs. Additionally, understanding how standards support sustainability initiatives – such as resource efficiency and ethical practices – enables SMEs to align their operations with broader societal goals, enhancing their reputation and competitiveness.

The HEIs can play a key role by integrating standardisation into their curricula, providing students with the necessary skills and knowledge to drive sustainability in SMEs. Additionally, non-formal education, such as workshops and professional development courses, can offer flexible learning opportunities tailored to the needs of SME employees. Finally, SMEs value graduates who understand the strategic potential of standards in fostering innovation and growth. Educated professionals should be able to identify opportunities where standards can drive research and development, improve product differentiation, and open new markets. They should also be prepared to advocate for SME interests in standardisation processes, ensuring that standards reflect the needs of smaller businesses.

In the short term, these educational efforts empower SMEs to understand and apply standards more effectively, enabling them to improve product and process quality and meet sustainability goals. In the long term, they boost operational efficiency, ensure regulatory compliance, foster sustainable development, and enhance market competitiveness. By equipping future professionals with these skills, education institutions can bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world application, empowering SMEs to benefit from using standards.

² In this section, the position of the Small Business Standards is expressed.

2. Hierarchical model of Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) in accordance with competencies and skills needed by the industry

ILOs, defined in D2.1., regarding industry needs and European values, green and digital skills, can also be divided into four KAs. The first analysis is related to the suitability of the ILOs for the HEIs. In the model (see Figure 1), ILOs are divided into four KAs with the primary intention of showing the potential limitation of HEIs in achieving them without collaboration and support from NSBs or other Standard Development Organizations (SDOs). Based on this analysis, ILOs in KA1. *Basic knowledge of standardisation is needed to raise awareness* and KA2. *Standardisation interdependencies and roles in specific contexts* are more academic and feasible to be fulfilled in HEIs. However, some ILOs are related to KA3. *Strategic use of standards* and KA4. *Strategic participation in standards development* can be fulfilled with the support of the NSBs or SDOs.

For example, the ILO related to participation in Technical Committees (TCs) and Working Groups (WGs), as observers or participants (S5.7 and S6.1) might confuse academics. Participation in WGs and TCs is possible without any knowledge and experience (expertise) in standardisation. For example, many industry experts, highly knowledgeable in their sectors, do not have expertise in standardisation. As a collective activity, standardisation has an institutional framework with professionals who know processes and procedures for standards development. They can, and they regularly provide training and support to the experts. In the context of the ITCoS, education on standardisation is a prerequisite for strategic participation, increasing the chances of influencing standardisation processes and outcomes. Support of the NSBs is also needed to provide access to standards for educational purposes.

Standardisation is a practical discipline, and it is essential to bring standardisation practice into the classroom. The primary collaborative activity between HEIs and NSBs revolves around providing access to standards. This access should not be limited to researchers and teachers specializing in standardisation but should extend to all researchers. By granting researchers access to SDOs, these organizations also become more appealing to companies, driven by the critical goal of knowledge acquisition (Blind, 2018; Blind and Mangelsdorf 2016).

To fulfil the industry and societal needs, e.g., to increase the number of people with competencies who can influence the standardisation process strategically, certain experience in standardisation is needed. Some sense of ways of influencing standardisation outcomes in formal organizations for standardisation can be achieved through different collaboration activities with NSBs, like student technical committees, internships and student training. However, bringing standardisation practice into the classroom might be more suitable with carefully planned gamification and flipped classrooms. Still, the learning objective related to strategic influence on the standardisation process might be overambitious to be achieved within HEIs.

Figure 1. Hierarchical Model of ILOs in accordance with the Competencies and Skills needed by the Industry

Among standardisation professionals, there is a belief that – “masters of standardisation are not needed” – it is better to enlarge the group of people who are aware of the usefulness of standardisation and acquaint possible future decision-makers with the subject (Simons, 1999). However, the level of education about standardisation in higher education can be significantly higher than only raising awareness.

According to Bloom’s Taxonomy (Bloom, 1994) (explained in D2.1) skills in the cognitive domain revolve around knowledge, comprehension and critical thinking of a particular topic, in general, three different levels can be identified, i.e., acquisition of factual knowledge, application of the acquired knowledge, and analysis, synthesis and evaluation of knowledge. Ex-cathedra lecturing (based on one-way communication in a classroom, in a blended learning environment or online) can provide only short-span learning outcomes. If the acquisition of factual knowledge is desired, then interaction with learning content is the most influential (Mijatović et al., 2012). Higher levels of learning outcomes need more communication and two-way interaction. Application of knowledge is based on the understanding of teaching content. Application of knowledge can be achieved through learning-by-doing, practical assignments, adequate internships and field trips, and connections with professionals (e.g., mentoring by professionals when working on assignments). Furthermore, involvement in more challenging activities (e.g., problem-solving and case studies), to reach more demanding learning objectives (e.g., analysis, synthesis, and evaluation) and increase students’ need for student-teacher and student-student interaction. The teaching methods depend on levels of generality of educational content, meaning that teaching general (e.g., related to all disciplines) and specific aspects of standardisation need different teaching methods. The hierarchical model of ILOs in accordance with the generality of teaching content is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Hierarchical Model of Intended Learning Outcomes ILOs in accordance with the Generality of Teaching Content

3. The Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation (ITCoS)

Several initiatives intended to develop uniform concepts for education about standardisation (e.g., United Nations Economic Commission for Europe – UNECE and Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation – APEC) have had very limited success among HEIs in Europe. The reasons for that might be their inability to find an adequate perspective for education on standardisation (e.g., the point of view of regulatory authorities dominant in Eastern European countries vs. the point of view of companies dominant in Western European countries) (Jachia et al., 2020). No matter how perfectly a concept is designed, its success depends on how well it manages to evoke a reaction and do what it is intended to do. This concept is not another abstract approach that will solve all educational problems. At its core, it relies on a practical approach that will be the basis for increasing engagement in education about standardisation in higher education.

There is an obvious need to increase the number of students who are educated in standardisation. The key challenge is to combine the efforts of HEIs in Europe to increase the number of graduates who enter the labour market with awareness and knowledge related to standardisation. *There is no simple and one way to engage HEIs in standardisation; involving academia is not only about engaging researchers, students and teachers but also programme managers and decision-makers. A long-term strategy is needed which takes a 10–15-year horizon plan to deliver the requisite number of standards professionals for future European market needs* (Assunção et al., 2023).

Education can bridge the gap between researchers, industry, SDOs, and academia. A lot of experience and educational material has been created in SDOs, representing a significant basis for disseminating knowledge about standardisation in HEIs. Visiting lecturers from SDOs is one of the important ways to transfer knowledge, but it rarely happens that content of standardisation continues to be taught by a university professor. Research is one of the ways in which the involvement of university professors in standardisation is possible. The seriousness of a new discipline and its value for inclusion in teaching are also assessed based on the quality and popularity of research publications. HEIs respond to market needs, new programs will not be established, nor new courses, if there is no clear picture of market needs. That is why we must constantly seek answers to the questions of how much knowledge is needed and what standardisation knowledge is in demand in the market.

3.1. What is the ITCoS?

The Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation Education (ITCoS) is a multidimensional approach intended to effectively guide the development of new educational curricula (or their parts) and content while benchmarking the existing ones. It aims to support versatile, attractive, and high-quality standardisation education, making it the most comprehensive and effective approach in the field.

The ITCoS is based on industry needs and social expectations. The KAs are defined according to studies of industry needs on education about standardisation and social expectations, which are related to the EU values (see more in D2.1), enhancing competitiveness through innovation in a sustainable environment, thus focusing on green and digital transition (Figure 3).

KAs in the ITCoS enable a way to systematize knowledge and skills related to standardisation, as well as, topics, existing teaching material (recommended books and research papers, teaching case studies, serious games, video material) and teachers' experiences (good practice).

The ITCoS is based on four KAs:

- › KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness
- › KA2. Standardisation interdependencies with other areas and roles in specific contexts
- › KA3. Strategic use of standards
- › KA4. Strategic participation in standards development

Figure 3. The Innovative Teaching Concept of Standardisation Education (ITCoS)

Knowledge Area KA1. *Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness* is dedicated to systematizing knowledge and skills, as well as topics, existing teaching material and existing experiences (good practice) of teachers in fundamentals of standardisation. If the objective is that a bachelor's or master's degree student understands the concept of standards and standardisation, a student must be motivated (want to understand); the desire to understand is encouraged through the conviction of the importance and context in which the concept of standardisation is observed. For business students, the motive for a deeper understanding will be gained through understanding the importance of standardisation in a business context, while for technology law students or engineering students, the perspective might be different. Knowledge Area KA1. is needed to raise awareness and it provides systematized knowledge on five main questions (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Knowledge Area KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness

Knowledge Area KA2. *Standardisation interdependencies and roles in specific contexts* systematize knowledge of interdependences and roles of standardisation in different contexts, e.g., regulatory framework, innovation, market, etc. Topics in this area overlap and show different perspectives. Knowledge Area KA3. *Strategic use of standards* is dedicated to the use of standards generally and specifically through topics of addressing implications and impacts of standards application, motives for and barriers to implementation of standards and specific skills related to finding the right standard. Knowledge Area KA4. *Strategic participation in standards development* deals with topics related to the implications and impacts of participation in standards development and skills related to participation in Technical Committees (TCs) and Working Groups (WGs), as well as identification of needs for new standards (Table 3).

Knowledge Areas (KA)	Industry and Market Needs for Education on Standardisation (Company Perspective) (Blind & Drechsler, 2017)	Knowledge Areas Topics
<p>KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness</p>	<p>To know the basic terms used in standards and standardisation</p> <p>To know the standardisation institutions.</p> <p>To be able to search for and select appropriate standardisation organizations.</p> <p>To be able to judge which form of standardisation (formal vs. consortia) is appropriate</p> <p>To know the standardisation institutions' processes.</p> <p>To know the history of standardisation.</p>	<p>1. Why standards and standardisation are important?</p> <p>1.1. Topic: The Strategic Importance of Standards and Standardisation</p> <p>1.2. Topic: Technical, economic, legal, and societal implications and impact of standards implementation and participation in standards development (the European point of view)</p> <p>1.3. Topic: History of Standardisation</p> <p>2. What are Standards and Standardisation?</p> <p>2.1. Topic: Concept of Standards and Standardisation</p> <p>2.2. Topic: General objectives of standardisation, roles and domains of standardisation</p> <p>2.3. Topic: Types of Standardisation and Classification of Standards</p> <p>3. Who uses standards?</p> <p>3.1. Topic: Users of standards</p> <p>4. Who develops standards?</p> <p>4.1. Topic: Who develops standards?</p> <p>4.2. Topic: Consortia-based Standardisation</p> <p>4.3. Topic: Company Standardisation</p> <p>5. How standards are developed (basics)?</p> <p>5.1. Topic: How standards are developed within SDOs in Europe?</p> <p>5.2. Topic: How standards are developed within SDOs internationally?</p>
<p>KA2. Standardisation interdependencies and roles in specific contexts</p>	<p>To be able to understand the interactions between standards and the regulatory framework</p> <p>To be able to understand standardisation in the context of the national quality infrastructure and</p>	<p>6. European System of Standardisation</p> <p>6.1. Topic: European System of Standardisation</p> <p>7. Interdependencies between Standardisation and Research</p> <p>7.1. Topic: Interdependencies between</p>

	<p>the macroeconomic environment</p> <p>Company standardisation</p>	<p>Standardisation and Research</p> <p>8. Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation</p> <p>8.1. Topic: Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation</p> <p>9. Interdependencies between Standards and Markets</p> <p>9.1. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Markets</p> <p>9.2. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Trade</p> <p>9.3. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Public Procurement</p> <p>9.4. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Policy</p> <p>9.5. Topic: Standards Battles</p> <p>10. Legal aspects of standardisation</p> <p>10.1. Topic: Legal aspects of standardisation</p> <p>11. SMEs and Standardisation</p> <p>11.1. Topic: SMEs and Standardisation</p> <p>12. Quality Infrastructure (QI)</p> <p>12.1. Topic: Quality Infrastructure (QI)</p> <p>12.2. Topic: The Role of Metrology in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)</p> <p>12.3. Topic: The Role of Standardisation in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)</p> <p>12.4. Topic: The Role of Accreditation in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)</p> <p>12.5. Topic: The Role of Conformity Assessment in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)</p> <p>12.6. Topic: The Role of Market Surveillance in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)</p> <p>13. European Values and Principles &</p>
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		Standardisation 14. Roles of Standardisation in Digital and Green Transformation
KA3. Strategic use of standards	To be able to understand the impact of implementing standards To be able to search for and select appropriate standards To be able to implement standards in product or process development	15. Motives for and barriers to applying standards 15.1. Topic: Motives for and barriers to applying standards 16. How to find the right standard? 16.1. Topic: How to find the right standard?
KA4. Strategic participation in standards development	To be able to understand the impact of standardisation processes To be able to identify the need for standards To be able to identify the need for getting involved in standardisation To be able to propose new work items in standardisation To be able to strategically influence the agenda in standardisation processes To be able to be passively involved in standardisation processes (observer) To be able to be actively involved in standardisation processes (participant)	17. Motives for and barriers to participating in standards development 17.1. Topic: Motives for and barriers to participating in standards development 18. How to participate in Technical Committees (TCs) and Working Groups (WGs)? 18.1. Topic: How to participate in Technical Committees (TCs) and Working Groups (WGs)? 19. How to identify the need for a new standard or improvement of an existing one? 19.1. Topic: How to identify the need for a new standard or improvement of an existing one?

Table 3. Initial Topics in Knowledge Areas

Following the Humboldtian idea, the ITCoS connects education and research on standardisation, bearing in mind that the university's role is to teach students critical thinking through the integration of research and teaching, with the primary goal of advancing knowledge. Research on standardisation is an essential support for expanding academic education on standardisation. Teachers at research universities are often motivated by research papers and case studies to include standardisation content in their courses. We have identified more than one thousand published research papers on standardisation, recognized their educational potential and connected over 300 published research papers with the topic of the ITCoS (Appendix 1). Some research papers can initiate new topics for educational purposes.

Formal education and professional training are different, but in the case of standardisation, individual NSBs have significant training experience and developed training materials (videos, serious games, etc.) that can be used in teaching. On the other hand, professionals from NSBs can be guest lecturers and thus bring the world of standardisation closer to students. However, the teachers and NSBs themselves will decide on the cooperation itself and its modalities. We now know that content and experiences are fragmented and that much of the content that exists and is even publicly available is little known to the academic public.

The support of colleagues and the exchange of experience or recommendations can significantly motivate teachers to include content from standardisation in their courses. The role of peer support is also to establish a network of teachers teaching standardisation who will continue to share experiences (connected with activities in WP4).

There are many definitions of teaching. Many aspects frame teaching at modern universities, and there are many different teaching practices. In education, teaching is the concerted sharing of knowledge and experience, which is usually organized within a discipline and, more generally, the provision of stimulus to a person's psychological and intellectual growth by another person or artefact (Impedovo & Iaquina, 2013). The aim of this concept (which follows the Humboldtian idea) is not to propose any specific way of teaching but it recommends student-centric approaches and active teaching methods.

In recent years, one of the directions in the development of teaching content that is interesting to students and has substantial educational potential is gamification. In standardisation and related disciplines, we have identified over twenty games that lecturers can use. How successful serious games will be depends on clearly defining why they are used and what is to be achieved. Monitoring the effects of serious games is very important, and experience is growing in recognising the effects of gamification efforts.

The concept of *serious games* is most easily described as games that go beyond pure entertainment and into the realm of learning. Serious games are applied games with a purpose and clear learning outcomes that link theory to practice, making complex topics easier and more 'hands-on'. Generally, this happens by strategically designing a game around some central knowledge or experience that players take part in and hopefully learn from. Games can create tacit knowledge and skills through a realistic, live simulation by introducing unpredictability, inviting interaction, and fostering individual contributions.

Serious games can take many forms, and in the last 20 years, the use of digital games has surged alongside the digitalisation of society. Still, the "old-fashioned" approach of board games is alive and can, in many cases, be more beneficial. This is partly because serious games can be something more than just the game itself. It is an exercise in sharing knowledge and collaboratively coming up with new ideas. It is about engaging with something that matters – in a new way; and, importantly, it lets learners have some fun at the same time. It is beneficial to meet up to play and learn together when possible for this to happen.

There are many reasons why games can be powerful tools for learning. First, it is something new, something different – games can break up the routine and provide a more enjoyable approach to learning. Participants can actively do something, developing their own learning rather than simply listening or reading. Beyond this, serious games have the potential to leverage some of the most powerful, scientifically sound approaches to learning and development. This is realized through utilising theories of learning, group processes, and change.

3.2. Placing theoretical ITCoS into Practice – the EDU4standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool

Standardisation is a practical and dynamic discipline, and the ITCoS can be just a theoretical concept if no activities place it into practice. The primary rationale behind the ITCoS is to support teachers in getting involved in standardizing content in their courses. To do so, the ITCoS will be a starting point for the development of the EDU4standards.eu teachers' support tool based on a web platform will provide search options based on ILOs (knowledge/skills D2.1), topics, type of teaching materials (information about recommended books, papers, case studies, ..., etc.). The EDU4standards.eu teachers' support tool will enable continual improvements of the ITCoS and provide the development of new topics.

The main intention of the EDU4standards.eu teachers support tool, based on the ITCoS, is to become a focal point – the foundation for exchanging information, good practices and experiences, as well as teaching material related to standardisation by educators to improve existing courses (or their parts) on standardisation or to inspire and support the involvement of standardisation topics/content in existing courses on different disciplines. This guide provides key topics and concepts, recommendations for sources, support material, and good practice for tailoring part of the course or the whole course on standardisation. The EDU4standards.eu teachers support tool will start with the content defined in Appendix 1 and will be further developed.

The ITCoS is the basis for developing the EDU4standards.eu teachers support tool. Still, at the same time, the EDU4standards.eu teachers' support tool is how the ITCoS will be constantly improved, which will be the basis for developing new topics and recording new experiences. At the end of the project, this will allow us to improve our knowledge of standardisation education and create a lessons-learned report. In Appendix 1, the initial content of the EDU4standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool, based on the ITCoS, is presented. The format for developing topics of the EDU4standards.eu teachers support tool is presented in Table 4.

Structure of the ITCoS guide	Explanation
1. Topic	Topics are chosen to represent a unit that the educators can combine with other units of their choice. The topics are intertwined. It is recommended that all topics have SGD (social/green/digital) examples.
2. Short instruction	Short instructions elaborate on why understanding a specific topic is important or relevant
3. The ILOs examples	In this section is explained the connection with ILOs published in D2.1 (see Appendix 2)
4. Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious games/Other	The teaching case studies do not have to be written (although that would be good), but they can be described in a few sentences, and a list of sources can be given for a specific case (for example, HD vs Blue Ray). Sharing teaching case studies used in a classroom is a practice we must support.
5. Good practice	Good practice is a description of educators' experience in working with students/trainees. All partners and pilots should contribute to this part.
6. Recommended sources	It lists literature (books, papers) that is recommended to someone who wants to start teaching standardisation or to improve existing classes.

Table 4. Format for the Topics in the EDU4standards.eu Teachers Support Tool

3.3. Fast forward – Relevant literature (books) on standardisation

When considering proposing a new course or including a new topic in an existing course, most university teachers need to research existing written material about the topic. Often, the first step is looking for relevant literature (textbooks) that would be good teaching material. In standardisation, some literature can be recommended for further exploration or to start. In this review, we mentioned just a few more general books.

- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition.

Readers of this textbook are not required to have any previous knowledge about standardisation. They are first introduced to the key concepts of standards and standardisation, different elements of the ecosystem and how they interact, and the procedures required for the production of standardisation documents. Then, readers are taken to the next level by addressing aspects related to standardisation, such as innovation, strategy, IPR, business, and economics. The teaching resources comprise this textbook, which conveys the main theoretical knowledge. The text is enriched with examples from actual standardisation practice to illustrate the key theoretical concepts. Furthermore, the book includes case studies, where the “case” can be a standardisation document, an event or action, or a company that implemented a particular practice that is related to standardisation. Each case study is intended to make readers reflect on a subset of the book’s learning objectives and messages, and it could potentially be used by lecturers as a building. Case

studies also enable students to see the concepts' application better and allow a classroom environment that promotes group discussion and interaction among students. Each chapter also includes a quiz to be used as a self-assessment learning activity. The contents of the book can be read in different ways. It can be read from cover to cover linearly, or readers may only focus on the specific chapters they are interested in. This is supported by the modular structure of the textbook, making the single chapters self-contained units that can be studied independently of other chapters. Each chapter begins with a list of learning objectives and key messages about what they will be learning in that particular chapter. For lecturers, this could be regarded as “meta-contents” to help decide which chapter of the book suits better the module or topic they are teaching.

- › Busch L. (2013) *Standards: Recipes for Reality*. The MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, London, England.

The close relationship between standards and power lies at the heart of this book's analysis. While many standards may seem neutral, harmless, purely technical, and disconnected from everyday life, they are, in fact, a largely unrecognized yet critical and expanding source of social, political, and economic power. In today's world, standards arguably represent one of the most significant expressions of power dynamics. This book delves into standards as the often-invisible frameworks that shape our technical, moral, social, and physical realities. They are the tools through which we construct the world around us. Standards govern nearly every aspect of modern life—from professional accreditation to environmental policies, consumer products, animal welfare, infrastructure safety, healthcare, education, and beyond. Each standard is the product of intense debate and negotiation. In this work, Lawrence Busch explores standards as “recipes for reality,” arguing that they influence not only the physical environment but also our social interactions and even our identities. He demonstrates how standards are inherently tied to power, often enabling some while disadvantaging others. Busch traces the history of formal standardization and explains how modern science became linked to the technical project of standardizing with moral aspects in it. Taking a comprehensive and integrated approach, Busch highlights how standards for both people and objects are deeply interconnected, and how they function simultaneously as technical, social, moral, legal, and ontological constructs.

- › Danish Standards Foundation. (2015). *A World Built on Standards, A Textbook for Higher Education*. https://www.ds.dk/media/px5jhney/a-world-built-on-standards.pdf?srsId=AfmBOoryuhKRx-O_E6dp0tUyjdF-2og6kLGgk2ONHVylBoO1XttkVQUd.

This publication is the result of work carried out by the *British Standards Institute, Danish Standards, the National Standards Authority of Ireland, the Finnish Standards Association and the University of Zagreb* under the auspices of the *CEN and CENELEC Joint Working Group for Education about Standardisation* to support education about standards and standardisation in Europe. *A World Built on Standards* is supported by multiple choice questions, PowerPoint presentations and Case Studies that can be used in teaching about standards and standardisation. After each chapter in the textbook, questions that can be used as discussion points on matters related to the chapter are provided. This publication and all supporting material can be found online and free of charge at www.ds.dk/education. This publication and all supporting material can be distributed but are not intended for commercial use.

- › De Vries, H. J. (1999). *Standardisation: A Business Approach to the Role of National Standardisation Organizations*. Springer Science+Business Media, LLC. <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9780792386384>

Even though it was published 25 years ago, this study remains a foundational work for understanding standardization. It is the first academic analysis of national standardization organizations, exploring their

history, modes of operation, and roles. Henk de Vries answers many questions relevant to preparing courses on standardization at the international, European, and national levels. This book covers a wide range of topics related to national standardization organizations, the concept of standards and standardization, stakeholders in standardization, actor behaviour in standardization, applications, and more.

- › Folmer, E., & Verhoosel, J. (2011). *State of the Art on Semantic IS Standardisation*. Interoperability & Quality, https://ris.utwente.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/5132324/Folmer-SOTA_web.pdf.

This study describes the state-of-the-art research on semantic IS standards and quality. It sets a foundation on which our and other research can contribute and make a knowledgeable contribution. The main research question is: What state-of-the-art research is available on the quality of semantic IS standards? We have chosen to perform a broad review of the state-of-the-art, including topics like economics and adoption of standards. Based on this state-of-the-art, we can define concepts for further studies, including standard, standard organization, interoperability, quality, and success of standards.

- › Gaillard, J. (1933). *A study of the fundamentals of industrial standardisation and its practical application, especially in the mechanical field*. <https://repository.tudelft.nl/record/uuid:eb5dd4a5-6b5a-4af5-ae8a-197de0cfc78>.

This study is valuable for understanding the origins of industrial standardization and for enhancing general knowledge about the essence of standardization. Over a century ago, Gaillard provided numerous definitions of standardization, many of which remain relevant to this day.

- › Hesser W., Feilzer A., & De Vries H. (2010). *Standardisation in Companies and Markets*, Helmut Schmidt University Germany, Erasmus University of Rotterdam, the Netherlands.

The textbook *Standardisation in Companies and Markets* is a result of the EU ASIA LINK project, led by Prof. Dr.-Ing. Wilfried Hesser from the Department of Standardisation and Technical Drawing/CAD at Helmut Schmidt University. Spanning 850 pages, it is the first interdisciplinary and most comprehensive book on standardization in companies and markets. The textbook includes 20 chapters, each reviewed and revised by international experts, covering topics across law, economics, and engineering. It provides an in-depth exploration of European and international standardization, including its history and principles. Written in an accessible style and enriched with numerous illustrations, the book examines key topics such as the economic strategies of standardization, the role of standards in corporate management, the impact of standardization on international economic relations in a globalized world, legal implementation at European and national levels, technical applications, and detailed case studies.

- › Murphy, C., & Yates, J. (2009). *The International Organization for Standardisation: Global Governance through Voluntary Consensus*. <https://www.routledge.com/The-International-Organization-for-Standardisation-ISO-Global-Governance-through-Voluntary-Consensus/Murphy-Yates/p/book/9780415774284?srsId=AfmBOopJ1JpQmsGKP74eM2CIWtpxMR453UNe6-RKY047tmGMn4oqBJqf>

The International Organization for Standardisation (ISO) is the first full-length study of the largest nongovernmental, global regulatory network whose scope and influence rivals that of the UN system. Much of the interest in the successes and failures of global governance focuses on high-profile organizations such as the United Nations, the World Bank, and the World Trade Organization. This volume is one of few books exploring the International Organization for Standardisation's (ISO) role as a facilitator of essential economic infrastructure and the implication of ISO techniques for a much broader realm of global governance.

Through detailing the initial rationale behind the ISO and a systematic discussion of how this low-profile organization has developed, Murphy and Yates, provide a comprehensive survey of the ISO as a powerful force on how commerce is conducted in a changing and increasingly globalized world.

- › Spivak, S., & Brenner, C. (2001). *Standardisation Essentials: Principles and Practice*. CRC Press. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1201/9781482277388>.

Interestingly, this book is among the most frequently cited works in research on standards and standardization. It offers comprehensive reference material, including definitions of key terms, clear explanations, and insights into how standards can both restrict trade and promote international commerce through the due process provisions of standards-writing organizations. The book also features real-world examples (from the history of modern standardisation) shared by experienced standards professionals, making it a practical resource.

- › Yates J., & Murphy C. N. (2019). *Engineering Rules: Global Standard Setting since 1880*. Hagley Library Studies in Business, Technology, and Politics. Johns Hopkins University Press. Baltimore.

If you want to Private, voluntary standards shape almost everything we use, from screw threads to shipping containers to e-readers. They have been critical to every major change in the world economy for more than a century, including the rise of global manufacturing and the ubiquity of the internet. In this study, JoAnne Yates and Craig N. Murphy trace the standard-setting system's evolution through time, revealing a process with an astonishingly pervasive, if rarely noticed, impact on our lives. Drawing on archival materials from three continents, Yates and Murphy describe the positive ideals that sparked the standardisation movement, the ways its leaders tried to realize those ideals, and the challenges the movement faces today. *Engineering Rules* is a riveting global history of the people, processes, and organizations that created and maintained today's economy's nearly invisible infrastructure, which is just as important as the state or the global market.

Table 5. provides recommendations:

- › for beginners who want to master the basics of standardisation quickly.
- › if there is a need to master what standardisation is essentially and there is a willingness to allocate a little more time, and
- › if there is an interest in the sociological or historical concept of standardisation with some prior knowledge of standardisation.

Table 5 shows which Knowledge Areas (KAs) are covered in which book. This information can only be used as a guide, and it is recommended to read these books.

Item	Beginners level	Intermediate level	Advanced level	KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness	KA2. Standardisation interdependencies with other areas and roles in specific contexts	KA3. Strategic use of standards	KA4. Strategic participation in standards development
Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice.		x		x	x	x	x
Busch L. (2013) Standards: Recipes for Reality.			x	x	x		
Danish Standards Foundation. (2015). A World Built on Standards, A Textbook for Higher Education.	x			x			x
De Vries, H. J. (1999). Standardisation: A Business Approach to the Role of National Standardisation Organizations.		x		x	x	x	x
Folmer, E., & Verhoosel, J. (2011). State of the Art on Semantic IS Standardisation. Interoperability & Quality.	x			x	x		
Gaillard, J. (1933). A study of the fundamentals of industrial standardisation and its practical application, especially in the mechanical field.			x	x	x		
Hesser W., Feilzer A., & De Vries H. (2010). Standardisation in Companies and Markets, Helmut Schmidt University Germany, Erasmus University of Rotterdam, the Netherlands.		x		x	x	x	x
Spivak, S., & Brenner, C. (1993). Standardisation Essentials: Principles and Practice. (1st edition). CRC Press.	x			x	x		
Yates J., & Murphy C. N. (2019). Engineering Rules: Global Standard Setting since 1880.			x	x			

Table 5. Essential Literature for Teaching Standardisation

4. Defining Priorities for addressing the Gaps in Knowledge needed for Standardisation Education

Standardisation is a practical discipline, and the majority of inputs for educational purposes come from the practice of standardisation and standards and research on the effectiveness of that practice on the market or reality. Many educational initiatives about standardisation are focused on formal standardisation, and aspects of *de facto* standardisation are often not in the limelight, however, without the point of view of large groups who develop standards or highly contribute to their development (e.g., professional or industrial associations, and consortia), aspects of the roles of standardisation in European and global competitiveness will not be clearly explained.

It is challenging to teach and learn about standards without the possibility of showing the standards to students. Many NSBs provide access to standards for HEIs, but the majority are still reluctant to do the same. A joint initiative in that direction might help to raise the issue of the accessibility of standards to educators and students. A good practice might be forming books with five to ten standards in specific disciplines so teachers can make standards closer to students.

Based on an analysis of good practices and resources suitable for education on standardisation, it can be seen that their number is still low even though excellent books are available. More high-quality teaching material is needed for standardisation in many specific disciplines (e.g., standardisation in blockchain or AI). The number of case studies adequate for education on standardisation is very low. Many students tend to be more inductive than deductive in their reasoning, meaning they grasp concepts more effectively through examples rather than by following a logical progression from fundamental principles.³ Incorporating examples and case studies can contribute to the effectiveness of teaching. However, ready-to-use case studies on standardisation are rare.

The voices of industry experts are rarely present in education on standardisation. Academics and SDOs provide the majority of written materials, but few cover the industry experts' positions. Research based on industry provides certain insight, but still, more industry experts' positions would be beneficial for education purposes. However, industry experts with substantial experience in standardisation are rare and concentrated in more developed European countries, so their inputs for education on standardisation need to be shared among HEIs in Europe.

5. Conclusions and Next Steps

As in the case of education in other disciplines, there is no single approach to standardisation education. The existence of many different education systems characterizes Europe. Many needs and interests intersect in education. In many EU countries, HEIs' operation is market-based, allowing students to choose the best programs and courses to prepare them for the best future. Even the attitude of students towards studying is different from HEI to HEI. The management of HEIs must balance between social and economic demands. It is not a question of whether the content from standardisation is needed in higher and vocational education but what it should be. Most experienced people in education would agree that it is all about good teaching, and everything depends on good and dedicated lecturers.

³ See more at <https://www.bu.edu/ctl/resources/teaching-resources/using-case-studies-to-teach/>.

Engaging standardisation in HEIs is a complex and time-consuming task requiring many actors' concentrated efforts. The ITCoS is dedicated to empowering teachers to include more content on standardisation or to better teach standardisation in their existing courses and programs. Based on task 2.3. and requirements for the ITCoS; in this document, we have analysed the rationale for the ITCoS and provide hierarchical models of ILOs in accordance with competencies and skills needed by the industry with a focus on possibilities that ILOs can be realized in HEIs and generality of topics.

The ITCoS is a multidimensional approach intended to effectively guide the development of new educational curricula (or their parts) and content while benchmarking the existing ones. It aims to support versatile, attractive, and high-quality standardisation education, making it the most comprehensive and effective approach in the field. It is based on industry needs and adheres to EU values, competitiveness, innovation, sustainability, and green and digital transition.

The ITCoS is based on four Knowledge Areas (KAs):

- › KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness
- › KA2. Standardisation interdependencies and roles in specific contexts
- › KA3. Strategic use of standards
- › KA4. Strategic participation in standards development

Furthermore, three aspects define the ITCoS – the connection of research on standardisation and education, the role of SDOs, and collegial support. Following the Humboldtian idea, the ITCoS connects education and research on standardisation, bearing in mind that the university's role is to teach students critical thinking through the integration of research and teaching, with the primary goal of advancing knowledge. Formal education and professional training are different, but in the case of standardisation, individual NSBs have significant training experience and developed training materials (e.g., videos, serious games, etc.) that can be used in teaching. The support of colleagues, through the exchange of experience or recommendations, can significantly motivate teachers to include content from standardisation in their courses.

The ITCoS can be just a theoretical concept if no activities place it into practice. The primary rationale behind the ITCoS is to support teachers in getting involved in standardizing content in their courses. To do so, the ITCoS will be a starting point for developing the EDU4standards.eu teachers' support tool based on a web platform. The EDU4standards.eu teachers' support tool will enable continual improvements of the ITCoS and provide the development of new topics. The EDU4standards.eu teachers' support tool is to become a focal point – the foundation for exchanging information, good practices, and experiences, as well as teaching material related to standardisation by educators, to improve existing courses (or their parts) on standardisation or to inspire and support the involvement of standardisation topics/content in existing courses on different disciplines. The initial content of the EDU4standards.eu teachers' support tool, based on the ITCoS is provided in Appendix 1.

The following steps will be related to establishing the EDU4standards.eu teachers' support tool and further exploring possible collaborations among HEIs on sharing experiences, NSBs and SDOs on sharing materials, and industry experts on finding the best ways to bring standardisation practices into classrooms. The information about the EDU4standards.eu teachers' support tool will be shared with the standardisation and academy community and will be open to all interested actors' contributions.

Appendix 1. The initial content of the EDU4standards.eu Teachers' Support Tool, based on the ITCoS

KA1. Basic knowledge of standardisation needed to raise awareness

1. Why standards and standardisation are important?

1.1. Topic: The Strategic Importance of Standards and Standardisation

Short instruction & Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Modern life is not possible without standards that are present all around us. You can plug all the electrical products you buy into the same socket, and each TV will receive a signal from the local broadcaster. To replace tyres on a car, you only need to know the marks – all manufacturers produce tyres following the dimensions and marking standards.⁴ At the same time, on the market full of products manufactured following the standards, it is possible to find many products of different quality, classes or types. Product standards do not define all product characteristics but only some important for the market. Imagine how good it would be if every cartridge fit every printer, regardless of manufacturer, just like you can buy printing paper from any manufacturer. There are plenty of varieties in their quality and prices, but they are all in the same format. All of them are in A4 format, which, like other A and B formats, was first defined by the DIN 476 standard, published in 1922. Welcome to the world of standardisation, where much work is still to be done (Mijatović, 2019).

There are plenty of examples which show the strategic importance of standards and standardisation in fostering economic growth, innovation, and global competitiveness, enhancing quality, safety, interoperability, and compatibility, and enabling access to the global market usually by reducing technical trade barriers.

According to the ETSI (2024), key reasons why it is important to teach the strategic importance of standardisation are:

- › Economic Competitiveness: Standardisation is a key driver of economic competitiveness. By adhering to recognized standards, industries enhance product quality, reduce costs, and streamline processes. Educating the workforce about these standards ensures that businesses remain globally competitive and can participate actively in international trade.
- › Innovation and Research: Standardisation fosters innovation by providing a common framework for the development and implementation of new technologies. A well-educated population is better equipped to engage in research and development activities that adhere to established standards, contributing to technological advancements and breakthroughs.

⁴ See more at

<https://www.etrto.org/getattachment/About-us/History/ETRTO-MORE-THAN-50-YEARS-OF-STANDARDISATION-2015-03-25.pdf?lang=en-US>.

- › Consumer Protection: Standardisation is crucial for ensuring the safety and quality of products and services, this includes the ever-increasing threats due to Cyber security. Educating consumers about the significance of standards empowers them to make informed choices, protecting their interests and fostering trust in the marketplace.
- › Global Trade Facilitation: International trade relies on standardized practices to ensure smooth cross-border transactions. By educating the workforce about global standards, businesses are able to seamlessly integrate into the international market, fostering economic growth and diplomatic relations.
- › Environmental Sustainability: Standards play a vital role in promoting sustainable practices and mitigating environmental impact. Integrating education on environmental standards prepares our citizens to contribute to sustainable development and address global challenges, such as climate change.

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K7.1., S6.6., S7.3.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Standards Are All Around You: Electronic Posters & Graphics
(American National Standards Institute – ANSI)

The electronic posters and graphical presentations are freely downloadable from the ANSI’s official website and can be used in introductory classes to raise awareness about technical solutions offered in standards – “Though hidden from sight in everyday life, standards are truly everywhere, working behind the scenes to assure that we can live, learn, play, and work safely and efficiently. Check out some of the places you can find standards”.

To learn more about ANSI’s electronic posters and graphics, please visit the following link:

- › <https://www.ansi.org/education/activities/standards-student-programs/k-12-students>

2. Standardisation Serious Game: IdeaMania (CEN)

Keywords: Standardisation, Standards

About: IdeaMania is online game aimed at increasing attention and awareness of standardisation, get target group interested in standardisation, improve impression of target groups to be favourable toward standardisation

Details:

- › Time to play: 3 - 5min per level, 3 levels
(Level 1: wind energy plant maintenance service Level 2: parcel box for postal services, Level 3: chemical exposure models)
- › Target group: researchers, startups, spinoffs
- › Group size:

Background: Created within BRIDGIT 2 (Bridging the Gap between Research & Standardisation)

Contact: christian.goroncy@din.de

Note for IdeaMania: Update in preparation

3. Standardisation Serious Game: NBN Business Game

Keywords: Standardisation in the context of product development.

Background: Hosted by NBN

About: The aim of the NBN Business Game is to get to know the value of standards in a broader context. The main context of the game is based on forging the ideal investment plan, creative tasks, teamwork, maximizing shareholder value, fun and reflection on the value of standards.

Details: To be played in groups of 2-5, max. 5 groups

- 60 min game + 30 min reflection
- Available in English

Contact: yens.van.overloop@nbn.be

Good practice:

The introduction of standardisation and standards might be a complex task, and starting with definitions might be confusing. Explanation of the presence of standards (and effects of their implementation, application or use) and their strategic importance in different contexts (e.g., for technological advancements, market creation etc.) can raise interest in the topic and enhance chances for understanding the meanings of standardisation and standards.

Recommended sources:

- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition, Chapter 8.
- › de Vries, H. J. (1999). Standardisation: A Business Approach to the Role of National Standardisation Organizations. Springer Science+Business Media, LLC. <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9780792386384>.
- › Hesser, W., Feilzer, A., & de Vries, H. J. (2010). Standardisation in Companies and Markets. Helmut Schmidt University. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337160610_Standardisation_in_Companies_and_Markets_3rd_Ed.
- › Spivak, S., & Brenner, C. (1993). Standardisation Essentials: Principles and Practice (First edition). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781482277388>.

Other sources on the information asymmetry (general):

- › Grillo, F., Wiegmann, P.M., de Vries, H.J., Bekkers, R., Tasselli, S., Yousefi, A., van de Kaa, G. (2024). Standardisation: Research Trends, Current Debates, and Interdisciplinarity. *Academy of Management Annals*, 18(2), 788-830.
- › Akerlof, G. A. (1970). The Market for “Lemons”: Quality Uncertainty and the Market Mechanism. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1879431>.
- › Montiel, I., Husted, B. W., & Christmann, P. (2012). Using private management standard certification to reduce information asymmetries in corrupt environments. *Strategic Management Journal*, 33(9), 1103-1113.
- › Nagurney, A., Li, D., & Nagurney, L. S. (2014). Spatial price equilibrium with information asymmetry in quality and minimum quality standards. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 158, 300-313.
- › Teece, D.J. (2018). Profiting from innovation in the digital economy: Enabling technologies, standards, and licensing models in the wireless world. *Research Policy*, 47(8), 1367-1387.

1.2. Topic: Technical, economic, legal, and societal implications and impact of standards implementation and participation in standards development (the European point of view)

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Both standards implementation and standards development have tremendous technical, economic, legal, and societal implications in Europe. Technical implications include ensuring quality and safety across industries (Abdelkafi et al., 2021), ensuring interoperability and compatibility of products, components, and services in technological systems (Baron & Spulber, 2018). By doing so, standards establish the basis for the introduction of new technologies (and innovations) and ensure that products, components and services supplied by different companies will be mutually compatible (Stroyan & Brown, 2012). Economic implications include enhancing overall competitiveness by reducing technical barriers to trade (Mangelsdorf, 2011), while enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of both export and trade within the European Single Market. Legal implications include ensuring compliance with EU regulations (e.g., European harmonized standards) (Blind & Mangelsdorf, 2016) while minimizing disputes over intellectual property through mechanisms such as FRAND or RAND licensing (Spulber, 2020). Societal implications include contributing to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDGs), thus ensuring that products, services, and processes support a resilient, green and digital EU Single Market (EC, 2022a).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.3., K7.1., K7.3., S6.6., S7.3.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. ISO Methodology 2.0

Although several studies explored the economic benefits of standards, comparing them might be difficult, due to differences in overall objectives, methodologies, as well as organizations conducting these studies. This might be one of the reasons why the International Organization for Standardisation (ISO) has developed a simple, step-by-step methodology and a robust set of tools to measure the economic benefits of standards. The primary scope of the ISO Methodology 2.0. is assessing the economic benefits of standards (e.g., the contribution of standards to the creation of economic value) for a company. ISO

methodology can be applied to all companies and industry sectors to identify the contribution that standards make to their performance (ISO, 2013).

To learn more about the ISO Methodology, please visit the following link:

- › <https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/archive/pdf/en/pub100344.pdf>

Good practice:

Quantitative approaches are rare in education on standardisation, but this should not be the case. Engaging students in evaluating the economic benefits of standards (e.g., by using a systematic approach of ISO Methodology) bridges theoretical knowledge with practical aspects of standards implementation. Evaluation of the economic benefits of standardisation is a challenging task; substantial time frame and quality of data are needed. A good practice is to provide a case study with quantitative data to students to make their conclusion. The experience with students in business and engineering studies is quite rewarding, it can raise their understanding of the complexity of economic impacts of standards implementation. Case studies that demonstrate how standards impact specific sectors, such as Manufacturing or ICT, thus enabling a clearer understanding of the role standards play in enhancing GDP and productivity are provided at the ISO website (not all with high quality).

Recommended sources:

- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition, Chapter 8.
- › Baron, J., & Spulber, D. F. (2018). Technology Standards and Standard Setting Organizations: Introduction to the Searle Center Database. *Journal of Economics and Management Strategy*, 27(3), 462–503. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jems.12257>.
- › David, P. (1987). Some new standards for the economics of standardisation in the information age. In M. Waterson, P. Dasgupta, & P. Stoneman (Eds.), *Economic Policy and Technological Performance*. (Vol. 98, Issue 392). <https://doi.org/10.2307/2233926>, pp. 857.
- › David, P., & Greenstein, S. (1990). The economics of compatibility standards: An introduction to recent research. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 1(1–2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/10438599000000002>, pp. 3–41.
- › Pham, T. H. (2006). Economic Aspects of Standardisation. In W. Hesser, Feilzer, & H. De Vries (Eds.), *Standardisation in Companies and Markets*. Helmut Schmidt University, Hamburg, pp. 77–123.
- › Spivak, S., & Brenner, C. (2001). *Standardisation Essentials: Principles and Practice*. CRC Press.
- › Stroyan, J., & Brown, N. (2012). Using Standards to Support Growth, Competitiveness and Innovation. In *Guidebook Series: How to Support SME Policy from Structural Funds*. (October).
- › Blind, K. (2004). *The Economics of Standards – Theory, Evidence, Policy*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar.
- › Swann, G.M.P. (2010). *The Economics of Standardisation: An Update*. <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a790abd40f0b679c0a0812d/10-1135-economics-of-standardisation-update.pdf>

- › Wiegmann, P.M., de Vries, H.J., Eom, D. (2023). Measuring societal impact of standards. Eindhoven: Eindhoven University of Technology.
https://pure.tue.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/299190300/Full_XXM_Report_2022_11_28.pdf.

1.3. Topic: History of Standardisation

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Standardisation has a long history and tradition. Through history, trade, wars and politics enhanced the need for standards and standardisation. One of the first written standards is The Eleusis Inscription which was created in the fourth century BC. It was discovered in 1893 in the area of Eleusis, 18 km northwest of present-day Athens. According to George Varoufakis (2010), the Eleusis Inscription is one of the first European standards that solved the problem of proving the quality of the bronze pins (polio) that were used to connect the discs of ancient columns. The Eleusis Inscription provides evidence that ancient Greeks applied strict specifications in orders related to bronze products (alloys primarily made of copper and tin, which may contain other elements). In this record, relationships between multiple producers are defined, committing to delivering the alloy according to given specifications and allowing customers to inspect the bronze quality through a clearly defined process agreed upon by all parties. This record specifically describes the alloy from which bronze wedges, used for connecting discus poles, will be made. Alongside the alloy specifications (1 part tin and 12 parts copper), the record provides guidelines for controlling compliance with the conditions. Varoufakis asserts that this standard defines an empirical method for controlling the quality of the materials supplied for the axles. It can be said that this is one of the first anticipatory standards that foresaw a problem that manufacturers might deceive buyers about the lesser amount of tin in the specified alloy (Varoufakis, 1999). The topics on the history of standardisation are important because they increase personal connection with the topics. This topic should cover the evolution of standards in specific contexts and emerging trends in standardisation.

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K7.1., S6.4., S7.3.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Case Study: History of Screws and Screwdrivers

Good practice:

The storytelling about milestones, such as the first unit of measurement, the establishment of early measurement systems (e.g., the metric system), the unified railway gauges, and the standardized screw base for light bulbs. Educators teaching about the history of formal standardisation can focus on its evolution from informal agreements to the establishment of formal organizations for standardisation, including ITU (1875), IEC (1907), and ISO (1947), and NSBs.

Recommended sources:

- › Clarke, C. (2005). The evolution of standardisation. *Automotive Production Systems and Standardisation: From Ford to the Case of Mercedes-Benz*.
- › Grossman, J. H. (2018). Standardisation (standardisation). *Critical Inquiry*, 44(3), 447-478.

- › Hawkins, R., Mansell, R., Skea, J., & Elgar, E. (1996). Standards, Innovation and Competitiveness: The Politics and Economics of Standards in Natural and Technical Environments. *Long Range Planning*, 3(29), 431.
- › Hesser, W. 2010. An Introduction – The History of Standardisation.
- › Varoufakis G. (1999). *Ancient Greek Standards – The History and Control of the Materials Which Left Their Mark on Greek Civilization*, Athens.
- › Verman, L. C. (1973). *Standardisation, a new discipline*. Archon Books.
- › Wenzlhuemer, R. (2010). *The History of Standardisation in Europe*.
- › Delimatsis, P., Bijlmakers, S., & Borowicz M.K. (2023) *The Evolution of Transnational Rule-Makers through Crises* (Ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- › Yates, J. & Murphy C.N. (2006). *Coordinating International Standards: The Formation of ISO*. <https://web.mit.edu/iandeseminar/Papers/Fall2006/Yates.pdf>.
- › Yates, J. & Murphy C. (2019). *Engineering Rules: Global Standard Setting Since 1880*. John Hopkins University Press.
- › Murphy, C.N. & Yates, J. (2009). *The International Organization for Standardisation (ISO) Global governance through voluntary consensus*. Routledge.

2. What are Standards and Standardisation?

2.1. Topic: Concept of Standards and Standardisation

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Generally, and highly simplified, the story goes like this. Some actors (e.g., companies, alliances of companies and organizations, research institutes, universities, and many other types of organizations) have a problem and need, for many distinct reasons, to find a solution with others. Some organizations – let’s call them standardisation organizations – provide a place and a specific framework (e.g., rules, process, project management) for actors to develop a joint solution. Finding a solution to common problems with others can happen outside the organization for standardisation. A company can create a joint solution by directly inviting other companies; this standardisation is often called standardisation based on cooperation. Sometimes actors create their own alliances in specific sectors and act by their own rules – that is the case of Consortia-based standardisation. However, the story is more complicated and much more interesting. Without standards, world trade will be impossible because “standards control access to virtually every market in global commerce and directly affect more than eighty per cent of world trade” (Purcell & Kushnier, 2016). There are many active standards organizations⁵ with thousands of members who develop tens of thousands of standards every year (Baron & Spulber, 2018). Some standardisation organizations provide a place for agreeing on solutions based on a consensus of many actors and are open to all actors interested in a solution. In those organizations, participation in standards development is voluntary, and the use of standards is voluntary. Due to their way of work and following principles of transparency, openness, impartiality and consensus, effectiveness and relevance, coherence, and the development dimension⁶ – those organizations are often called voluntary consensus-based organizations for standardisation. All

⁵ According to consortiuminfo.org there are more than 1120 active standards organizations, see more at <https://www.consortiuminfo.org>.

⁶ In 2000, the World Trade Organization’s Technical Barriers to Trade Committee (WTO TBT Committee) adopted the Six Principles for the Development of International Standards: transparency, openness, impartiality and consensus, effectiveness and relevance, coherence, and the development dimension. They are meant to help international standards work better for global trade and are widely followed by standards bodies seeking international relevance (see more at https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/tbt_e/principles_standards_tbt_e.htm).

standardisation activities begin when some actor(s) propose a solution to others. Then through the process, they come to a solution acceptable to everyone. Standards are not necessarily an expression of the highest expertise or requirements but rather an expression of what the parties involved could agree upon (Madelung & Andersen, 2013). That is why it is often said that standards do not contain the best practice or solutions for every participating actor but rather those with the highest degree of agreement – possible – at that moment.

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K7.1.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Serious Game: Standard Park (BSI)

Keywords: Standardisation, Standards

About: This game acts as an introduction to standards and standardisation for participants who have had no or truly little prior experience with the topic. It is a board game driven by the drawing of cards, in which players get to see the benefit of both applying standards and participating in a standardisation process. The narrative of the game follows a company that is hired by their city's mayor's office to construct a playground, encountering some common standards-related hurdles and opportunities along the way. The main learning objective for this game is that engaging in the use and development of standards represents a vast array of opportunities for businesses.

Details:

- › Time to play: 60-90 minutes.

- › Target group: No or limited prior standardisation knowledge.
- › Group size: 3-5 players per group.

Contact: magnus.hakvag@hoknowledge.com

Background:

Developed with and for the British Standards Institution (BSI) to engage young professionals in using standards and partaking in standardisation work.

2. Serious Game: Standards Journey (BSI)

Keywords: Standardisation, Standards

About: This process-based board game goes a step further than the Standard Park game in developing an understanding of the standardisation process. The game introduces the main steps of a BSI standardisation process along with key terms used by standards organizations during development. Players are tasked first with

building the standardisation process using tokens, before subsequently playing through this process following a narrative wherein, they control the actions of a large health technology company. The main learning objective of the game is for players to get an understanding of what each step of the standardisation process looks like and how they can contribute to the process (and benefit from it).

Details:

- › Time to play: 60-90 minutes.
- › Target group: Rudimentary prior standardisation knowledge
- › Group size: 3-5 players per group.

Background:

Developed with and for the British Standards Institution (BSI) to engage young professionals in using standards and partaking in standardisation work.

Contact: magnus.hakvag@hoknowledge.com

Good practice:

There are plenty of definitions of standards and standardisation. It is a challenging task to teach and understand the endless definitions. However, such richness in definitions of standardisation and standards can be a base for good class experience. Class discussion on the definitions (old and new ones) provided by formal organizations for standardisation, including international standardisation organizations (ISO/IEC/ITU), European standardisation organizations (CEN/CENELEC/ETSI), and National Standards Bodies (e.g., BSI, DIN, AFNOR, etc.) might be a good starting point. For example, the definition which describes a standard as a document, established by consensus, and approved by a recognized body (ISO/IEC, 2004),..., can be used to explain that not all standards are documents, established by consensus, and approved by a recognized body (Hesser et al., 2010) which can lead to other definitions provided by other organizations for standardisation (e.g., professional, industry, and business associations, consortia, and fora working in different fields). Enabling students to critically analyze different definitions significantly raises their understanding of the topic.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/what-standardisation-and-what-are-standards>

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › Grillo, F., Wiegmann, P.M., de Vries, H.J., Bekkers, R., Tasselli, S., Yousefi, A., van de Kaa, G. (2024). Standardisation: Research Trends, Current Debates, and Interdisciplinarity. *Academy of Management Annals*, 18(2), 788-830.
- › Baron, J., & Spulber, D. F. (2018). Technology Standards and Standard Setting Organizations: Introduction to the Searle Center Database. *Journal of Economics and Management Strategy*, 27(3), 462–503. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jems.12257>.
- › De Vries, H. J. (1999). *Standardisation: A Business Approach to the Role of National Standardisation Organizations*. Springer Science+Business Media, LLC. <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9780792386384>.
- › Gaillard, J. (1933). A study of the fundamentals of industrial standardisation and its practical application, especially in the mechanical field. <https://repository.tudelft.nl/record/uuid:eb5dd4a5-6b5a-4af5-ae8a-197de0cfc78>.
- › Hesser, W., Feilzer, A., & de Vries, H. J. (2010). *Standardisation in Companies and Markets*. Helmut Schmidt University. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337160610_Standardisation_in_Companies_and_Markets_3rd_Ed.

- › Murphy, C., & Yates, J. (2013). The International Organization for Standardisation: Global Governance through Voluntary Consensus. *Business Regulation and Non-State Actors: Whose Standards Whose Development*, 81–94. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203126929-15>.
- › Spivak, S., & Brenner, C. (1993). *Standardisation Essentials: Principles and Practice* (First edition). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781482277388>.
- › Wiegmann, P. M., de Vries, H. J., & Blind, K. (2017). Multi-Mode Standardisation: A critical review and a research agenda. *Research Policy*, 46(8), 1370–1386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2017.06.002>.
- › Wiegmann, P. M., Eggers, F., de Vries, H. J., & Blind, K. (2022). Competing Standard-Setting Organizations: A Choice Experiment. *Research Policy*, 51(2), 104427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2021.104427>.

2.2. Topic: General objectives of standardisation, roles and domains of standardisation

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

In today's highly complex arena of standardisation, it is not easy to define the general objectives, roles, and domains of standardisation. Today, each standard is developed with its general objectives (motives). Basically, the general objectives of standardisation include applying some scientific, research, and professional results, achieving common benefits through mutual understanding in society, and achieving order in a given context. Also, the objectives may be to prevent efforts to find something that already exists and share good practices and experiences. In business, the general objectives of applying standards are contributing to business results, increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization, and reducing the costs of products/services. Organizations use standards in their business because, sometimes, meeting the requirements of standards means the survival of their business. Many think that standardisation is purely technical discipline. Although the roots of standardisation may be found in the fields of electrical engineering and mechanical engineering, modern standardisation takes place in many fields, including telecommunications, environment, construction, information technology, management, social responsibility, sports, etc. Nowadays, there is no area of human activity in which standardisation activities do not take place. It is multidisciplinary, which is why it is necessary to look at it from the aspects of several different disciplines.

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K7.1.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Good practice:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Recommended sources:

- › de Vries, H. J. (1999). *Standardisation: A Business Approach*

to the Role of National Standardisation Organizations.

Springer Science+Business Media, LLC. <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9780792386384>.

- › Hesser, W., Feilzer, A., & de Vries, H. J. (2010). Standardisation in Companies and Markets. Helmut Schmidt University. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337160610_Standardisation_in_Companies_and_Markets_3rd_Ed.
- › Verman, L. C. (1973). Standardisation, a new discipline. Archon Books.

2.3. Topic: Types of Standardisation and Classification of Standards

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Considering that there is no general agreement about the classification of standards – there are several ways in which standards can be classified. One of the most consistent classifications of the standards is provided by Prof. De Vries. A systematic classification may be beneficial for SDOs, as they could describe standardisation projects, develop criteria to determine if standards are within their scope, and enhance the identification of standards (De Vries, 1999).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K7.1.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Case Study: Michelin Awards: Do the stars still matter?

<https://www.independent.co.uk/life-style/food-and-drink/features/michelin-awards-do-the-stars-still-matter-9137115.html>

Good practice:

Educators teaching the classification of standards usually classify standards as formal vs. informal standards thus explaining the differences between standards developed within formal organizations for standardisation (also known as de jure standards) and standards developed within informal organizations for standardisation (also known as de facto standards). Educators also address one of the most commonly used classifications of standards thus classifying standards as product, service, process, and management system standards (MSSs) (Stroyan & Brown, 2012). Other classifications are addressed if considering the economic effects of standards (e.g., according to the economic problems they resolve, standards may be classified as compatibility standards, minimum quality/safety standards, variety-reducing and information and measurement standards (David, 1987).

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/classifications-standards>
- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, URL:

https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf,
2nd Edition, Chapters 3 and Chapter 5.

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › David, P. (1987). Some new standards for the economics of standardisation in the information age. In M. Waterson, P. Dasgupta, & P. Stoneman (Eds.), *Economic Policy and Technological Performance*. (Vol. 98, Issue 392). <https://doi.org/10.2307/2233926>, pp. 857.
- › David, P., & Greenstein, S. (1990). The economics of compatibility standards: An introduction to recent research. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 1(1–2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/10438599000000002>, pp. 3-41.
- › De Vries, H. J. (2006). IT Standards Typology. In K. Jakobs (Ed.), *Advanced Topics in Information Technology Standards and Standardisation Research*. Idea Group Publishing, p. 4.
- › Egyedi, T.M., Ortt, J.R. (2017). Towards a functional classification of standards for innovation research. In R. Hawkins, K. Blind, R. Page (Eds.) *Handbook of Innovation and Standards*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar
- › Folmer, E., & Verhoosel, J. (2011). State of the Art on Semantic IS Standardisation, Interoperability & Quality.
- › Hesser, W. (2010). Standardisation within a Company: Strategic Perspective. In W. Hesser, A. Feilzer, & H. de Vries (Eds.), *Standardisation in Companies and Markets* (3rd ed.). Druckerei Helmut Schmidt University, pp. 569.
- › Pham, T. H. (2006). Economic Aspects of Standardisation. In W. Hesser, Feilzer, & H. De Vries (Eds.), *Standardisation in Companies and Markets*. Helmut Schmidt University, Hamburg, pp. 77-123.
- › Spivak, S., & Brenner, C. (2001). *Standardisation Essentials: Principles and Practice*. CRC Press.
- › Stroyan, J., & Brown, N. (2012). Using Standards to Support Growth, Competitiveness and Innovation. In *Guidebook Series: How to Support SME Policy from Structural Funds*. (October).

Other sources on de jure standards:

- › Backhouse, J., Hsu, C. W., & Silva, L. (2006). Circuits of power in creating de jure standards: Shaping an international information systems security standard. *MIS Quarterly*, 413-438.
- › Bartleson, K. (2012). What's The Difference Between De Jure and De Facto Standards? *Electronic Design*, 14.
- › Tamura, S. (2015). Who participates in de jure standard setting in Japan: The analysis of participation costs and benefits. *Innovation*, 17(3), 400-415.
- › Tamura, S. (2018). The dynamics and determinants of de jure standards: Evidence from the electronic and electrical engineering industries. *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, 56, 1-12.

Other sources on de facto standards:

- › Belleflamme, P. (2002). Coordination on formal vs. de facto standards: A dynamic approach. *European Journal of political economy*, 18(1), 153-176.
- › Den Uijl, S. (2015). The emergence of de-facto standards (No. EPS-2014-328-LIS).
- › Memarian, K., Matthiesen, J., Lingard, J., Nienhuis, K., Chisnall, D., Watson, R. N., & Sewell, P. (2016). Into the depths of C: elaborating the de facto standards. *ACM SIGPLAN Notices*, 51(6), 1-15.

Other sources on the anticipatory standardisation:

- › Cargill, C. F. (2011). Why standardisation efforts fail. *Journal of Electronic Publishing*, 14(1).
- › Egyedi, T. M., & Sherif, M. H. (2008, May). Standards' dynamics through an innovation lens: Next-generation Ethernet networks. In 2008 First ITU-T Kaleidoscope Academic Conference-Innovations in NGN: Future Network and Services (pp. 127-134). IEEE.
- › Umamathy, K., Puro, S., & Bagby, J. (2012). Empirical analysis of anticipatory standardisation processes: a case study. *Information Systems and E-Business Management*, 10.

Other sources on the concurrent standardisation:

- › Grote, G., Weichbrodt, J. C., Günter, H., Zala-Mezö, E., & Künzle, B. (2009). Coordination in high-risk organizations: the need for flexible routines. *Cognition, technology & work*, 11, 17-27.
- › Gühthert, K. Concurrent standardisation as a necessity: The genesis of the new official orthographic guidelines. In *Språknormering-i tide og utideti* (pp. 15-32). Novus AS.
- › Kim, H. J., Park, K. S., Chin, B. M., & Park, C. H. (1999). Virtual standards development environments for concurrent standardisation process. *ETRI Journal*, Vol. 21(1), pp. 55-71.
- › Laakso, M., & Kiviniemi, A. O. (2012). The IFC standard: A review of history, development, and standardisation, *Information Technology. ITcon*, Vol 17(9).

Other sources on the ex-ante standardisation:

- › Brander, J. A. (1995). Strategic trade policy. *Handbook of international economics*, 3, 1395-1455.
- › Choi, J. P. (1994). Standardisation and Experimentation: Ex Ante versus Ex Post Standardisation.
- › Contreras, J. L. (2011). An empirical study of the effects of ex-ante licensing disclosure policies on the development of voluntary technical standards. *National Institute of Standards and Technology*, No. GCR, 11-934.
- › Contreras, J. L. (2013). Technical Standards and „ex-ante“ Disclosure: Results and Analysis of an Empirical Study. *Jurimetrics*, Vol. x, pp. 63-211.
- › Galvin, P., & Rice, J. (2008). A Case Study of Knowledge Protection and Diffusion for Innovation: Managing Knowledge in the Mobile Telephone Industry. *International Journal of Technology Management*, 42(4), 426-438.
- › Geradin, D. (2006). Standardisation and technological innovation: Some reflections on ex-ante licensing, FRAND, and the proper means to reward innovators. *World Competition*, 29(4).
- › Geradin, D., & Layne-Farrar, A. (2007). The logic and limits of ex-ante competition in a standard-setting environment. *Competition Policy International*, 3(1).

Other sources on the ex-post standardisation:

- › Argentesi, E., Buccirosi, P., Calvano, E., Duso, T., Marrasso, A., & Nava, S. (2021). Merger policy in digital markets: an ex-post assessment. *Journal of Competition Law & Economics*, 17(1), 95-140.
- › Choi, J. P. (1994). Standardisation and Experimentation: Ex Ante versus Ex Post Standardisation.
- › Church, J., & Gandal, N. (2012). Direct and indirect network effects are equivalent: A comment on “Direct and Indirect Network Effects: Are They Equivalent?”. *International Journal of Industrial Organization (IJIO)*, Vol. 30(6), pp. 708-712.

Other sources on the voluntary consensus-based standardisation:

- › Egyedi, T. M. (2001). Beyond Consortia, Beyond Standardisation. New Case Material and Policy Threads. Final Report for the European Commission. Delft. The Netherlands.
- › Marpet, M. I. (1998). An ethical issue in voluntary-consensus standards development: A decision-science view. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 17, 1701-1716.
- › Murphy, C., & Yates, J. (2013). The International Organization for Standardisation: Global Governance through Voluntary Consensus. *Business Regulation and Non-State Actors: Whose Standards Whose Development*, 81–94. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203126929-15>.
- › Spencer, C., & Temple, P. (2016). Standards, learning, and growth in Britain, 1901–2009. *The Economic History Review*, 69(2), 627-652.
- › Van Elk, K., & van der Horst, R. (2009). Access to Standardisation. Study for the European Commission Enterprise and Industry Directorate-General, Final Report, Zoetermeer [10.03. 2009].

3. Who uses standards?

3.1. Topic: Users of standards

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important

Generally, there are two types of standard users: direct and indirect. Direct users are those who implement the standards – organizations or individuals who apply standards across a wide range of activities. Indirect users are those affected by the application of standards, such as consumers of products and services that comply with standards. Two aspects of standard users are receiving increased attention: the participation of indirect users in standards development and the influence of indirect users on the evolution of standards implementation. Standards are developed to be used, and a successful standard is one that is widely accepted in the market. Most experts involved in developing standards represent organizations that also implement them. However, the pool of direct users of standards (those who implement them) is larger than the pool of those who develop them. Gaining insight into the users of standards could be pivotal in understanding the needs of a particular standard. Yet, identifying who uses specific standards is not straightforward. Formal standardisation bodies do not collect data on who uses the standards, how they are used, or under what conditions.

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.2., K7.1.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Case Study: Why do we use QWERTY| You're Doing it Wrong! Episode 5 | BBC Ideas:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AB9-qdPO1Eg>

2. Many NSBs provide free access to standards to educational institutions.

Please contact your NSBs for more details, the complete list of the European NSBs can be found here:

- › <https://sbs-sme.eu/standards-and-smes/standardisation-bodies/>

Good practice:

To increase understanding of the role and power of users of standards the case on QWERTY keyboard can be used. The same case can be used for other topics too. The case QWERTY keyboard is good for explaining concepts installed base (in standardisation), dominant design, lock-in, and bandwagon effect.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/users-standards>

Other sources on the installed base:

- › Farrell, J., & Saloner, G. (1986). Installed base and compatibility: Innovation, product preannouncements, and predation. *The American Economic Review*, 940-955.
- › Kauffman, R. J., & Techatassanasoontorn, A. A. (2005). Does one wireless standard promote faster growth?. In *Proceedings of the 37th Hawaii International Conference on Systems Science*, Waikoloa, HI. IEEE Computing Society Press Los Alamitos, CA.
- › Schilling, M. (1999). Winning the standards race: Building installed base and the availability of complementary goods. *European Management Journal*, 17(3), 265-274.
- › Wang, S., Zheng, Y., & Wang, Q. (2023). Technical standardisation and total factor productivity in innovation-driven development: Evidence from China. *Plos one*, 18(10), e0287109.
- › Zoo, H., de Vries, H. J., & Lee, H. (2017). Interplay of innovation and standardisation: Exploring the relevance in developing countries. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 118, 334-348.

Other sources on the dominant design:

- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). *Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice*, ETSI 2021, URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition, Chapters 3 and Chapter 5.
- › Brem, A., Nylund, P. A., & Schuster, G. (2016). Innovation and de facto standardisation: The influence of dominant design on innovative performance, radical innovation, and process innovation. *Technovation*, 50, 79-88.
- › Brem, A., & Nylund, P. (2022). The inertia of dominant designs in technological innovation: An ecosystem view of standardisation. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 71, 2640-2648.
- › Costabile, C., Iden, J., & Bygstad, B. (2022). Building digital platform ecosystems through standardisation: an institutional work approach. *Electronic Markets*, 32(4), 1877-1889.
- › Fernández, E., & Valle, S. (2019). Battle for dominant design: A decision-making model. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 25(2), 72-78.
- › Murmann, J. P, Frenken, K. (2006). Toward a systematic framework for research on dominant designs, technological innovations, and industrial change, *Research Policy*, Vol. 35, pp. 925–952.

Other sources on the lock-in phenomenon:

- › Gillette, C. P. (1998). Lock-in effects in law and norms. *BUL Rev.*, 78, 813.

- › Haoqi, Q., Libo, W., & Weiqi, T. (2017). “Lock-in” effect of emission standard and its impact on the choice of market-based instruments. *Energy Economics*, 63, 41-50.
- › Kim, J. E., & Tang, T. (2020). Preventing early lock-in with technology-specific policy designs: The Renewable Portfolio Standards and diversity in renewable energy technologies. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 123, 109738.
- › Miller, J. S. (2006). Standard setting, patents, and access lock-in: RAND licensing and the theory of the firm. *Indiana Law Review*, 40, 2007-6.
- › Opara-Martins, J., Sahandi, R., & Tian, F. (2014, November). Critical review of vendor lock-in and its impact on adoption of cloud computing. In *International conference on information society (i-Society 2014)* (pp. 92-97). IEEE.
- › Unruh, G. C. (2000). Understanding carbon lock-in. *Energy policy*, 28(12), 817-830.

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › Abernathy, W. J. & Utterback, J. (1978). Patterns of industrial innovation. *Technology Review* 50, 41–47.
- › Bellis, M. (2011). Typewriters, QWERTY, and Typing. Accessed on 12.04.2011. Retrieved from: <https://inventors.about.com/library/inventors/brtypewriter.html/>.
- › Bigler J. C. (2014). The Dvorak Keyboard. Accessed on 11.02.2014. Retrieved from: <http://www.mit.edu/~jcb/Dvorak/>.
- › Brooks M. (2011), Introducing the Dvorak Keyboard, Accessed on 08.09.2011. Retrieved from: <http://dvorak.mwbrooks.com/>.
- › Liebowitz, S. J., & Margolis, S. E. (2014). Network Externalities (Effects). Accessed on 23.10.2022. Retrieved from: <https://personal.utdallas.edu/~liebowit/>
- › Murmann, J. P, Frenken, K. (2006). Toward a systematic framework for research on dominant designs, technological innovations, and industrial change, *Research Policy* 35 (2006) 925–952.
- › Purcell, D. & Kushnier, G. (2016). Globalization and Standardisation. *The Journal of SES – The Society for Standards Professionals*. Accessed on 09.11.2022. Retrieved from: <http://www.standardsuniversity.org/e-magazine/august-2016-volume-6/globalization-and-standardisation/>.
- › SBS. (2020). Annual Report. Accessed on 09.11.2022. Retrieved from: https://www.sbs-sme.eu/sites/default/files/publications/SBS%20Annual%20Report%202020_1.pdf.
- › SBS. (2022). SME Compatibility Test for Standards. Accessed on 09.11.2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.sbs-sme.eu/sme-compatibility-test-standards-1>.

4. Who develops standards?

4.1. Topic: Who develops standards?

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Many actors develop standards, influence their development, or contribute to the global world of standardisation. Organizations for standardisation provide a platform for representatives of different actors (e.g., companies, universities, research institutes, representatives of consumers, etc.) to join their efforts to develop standards. In standardisation, representatives of organizations who need to have expert knowledge are called experts. The people who work in organizations for standardisation are often called standardisation professionals. Standardisation professionals do not participate in developing solutions, but

they provide the framework for experts to work following rules, and they manage the standards development processes. From a general point of view, all organizations that develop standards can be classified as formal and informal. The political or governmental body recognizes formal organizations as international, regional, and national organizations for standardisation. Formal standardisation is often called voluntary consensus-based standardisation meaning that standards are developed and used voluntarily within a consensus-based process which means that the process is open and accessible for all parties interested, and all interests are attempted to be met through agreement. Informal organizations for standardisation are all other organizations for standardisation except international, regional, or national organizations that are appointed or recognized by the governments. However, this point might be blurred because many professional or industrial associations (e.g., IEEE, ASTM, ASME, etc.) are considered informal even though their predecessors participated in establishing international organizations for standardisation. Organizations that develop standards create a dynamic and complex network. Formal and informal organizations for standardisations collaborate. The case of GS1 standards shows that it takes many organizations to agree upon one solution to become international standards. In this case, market acceptance of simple but unique solutions (bar codes) and technologies for machine identification was substantial when the solution became an international standard.

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K7.1.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Case Study: GS1 System of Standards

Good practice:

Educators teaching students about who develops standards usually explore the roles of key players, including international organizations for standardisation (ISO/IEC/ITU), European organizations for standardisation (CEN/CENELEC/ETSI), National Standards Bodies (e.g., BSI, DIN, AFNOR, etc.), but also other organizations, such as professional associations, industry associations, business associations, consortia, and fora, including but not limited to IEEE, ASTM, ASME, API, OASIS, Wi-Fi Alliance, W3C, Bluetooth Special Interest Group (SIG), etc. They use examples to explore how formal and informal organizations for standardisation may collaborate but also use case studies to explore how standards developed by various organizations may lead to standard battles. They may also use serious games to simulate the standards development process thus emphasizing how standards development fosters inclusive decision-making, thus balancing diverse interests.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/who-develops-standards>
- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition, Chapters 3 and Chapter 4.

Other sources on standards development:

- › Balzarova, M. A., & Castka, P. (2012). Stakeholders' influence and contribution to social standards development: The case of multiple stakeholder approach to ISO 26000 development. *Journal of business ethics*, 111, pp. 265-279.
- › Beeler, G. W. (1998). HL7 Version 3—An object-oriented methodology for collaborative standards development. *International journal of medical informatics*, 48(1-3), 151-161.
- › Bijlmakers, S. (2021). No ISO-fix for Human Rights: A Critical Perspective on ISO 26000 Guidance on Social Responsibility. In: Marx, A., Van Calster, G., Wouters, J., Otteburn, K. & Lica D. *Research Handbook on Global Governance, Business and Human Rights*. Edward Elgar. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781788979832>.
- › Clapp, J. (1998). The Privatization of Global Environmental Governance. ISO 14000 and the Developing World. *Global Governance*, 4(3), 295-316, https://www-jstor-org.tilburguniversity.idm.oclc.org/stable/27800201?seq=1#metadata_info_tab_contents.
- › Hallström, K.T. (2004). Organizing international standardisation: ISO and the IASC in the quest of authority. In *Organizing International Standardisation*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- › Haufler, V. (1999). Negotiating International Standards for Environmental Management System: the ISO 14000 standards. UN Vision Project on Global Public Policy Networks. New York. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/237466208_Negotiating_International_Standards_for_Environmental_Management_Systems_The_ISO_14000_Standards.
- › Hoel, T., & Mason, J. (2018). Standards for smart education – towards a development framework. *Smart Learning Environments*, 5(1), 1-25.
- › Maisonneuve, J., Deschanel, M., Heiles, J., Li, W., Liu, H., Sharpe, R., & Wu, Y. (2009). An overview of IPTV standards development. *IEEE Transactions on broadcasting*, 55(2), 315-328.
- › Morikawa M. & Morrison J. (2004). Who Develops ISO Standards? A Survey of Participation in ISO's International Standards Development Process. Pacific Institute. https://pacinst.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/02/iso_participation_study2.pdf.
- › Mikulich. (2023). ISO 14000-14001, The Developing World's Perspective. *Tulane Environmental Law Journal* 17(1), 117-162.
- › Volpato, A. & Eliantonio, M. (2024). The participation of civil society in ETSI from the perspective of throughput legitimacy. *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13511610.2024.2321852>
- › Waguespack, D. M., & Fleming, L. (2009). Scanning the common Evidence on the benefits to startups participating in open standards development. *Management Science*, 55(2), 210-223.
- › Weiss, M., & Cargill, C. (1992). Consortia in the standards development process. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science* 43, No. 8 (1992): 559-565.
- › Wiegmann, P. M., de Vries, H. J., & Blind, K. (2017). Multi-Mode Standardisation: A critical review and a research agenda. *Research Policy*, 46(8), 1370–1386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2017.06.002>.
- › Wiegmann, P.M. (2019). Becoming the industry standard when standardisation is not standardized. <https://www.rsm.nl/discovery/2019/industry-standard/>.

This is an accessible summary with a nice video of the Research Policy paper on multi-mode standardisation cited above.

Other sources on Standards Development Organizations (SDOs):

- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition, Chapters 3 and Chapter 4.
- › Baron, J., Contreras, J. L., Husovec, M., Larouche, P., & Thumm, N. (2019). Making the rules: The governance of standard development organizations and their policies on intellectual property rights. JRC Science for Policy Report, EUR, 29655.
- › Baron, J., Contreras, J. L., & Larouche, P. (2021). Balance requirements for standards development organizations: A historical, legal and institutional assessment. *University of Utah College of Law Research Paper*, (430).
- › Baron, J. & Kanevskaia, O. (2023). Global Rivalry Over the Leadership in ICT Standardisation: SDO Governance Amid Changing Patterns of Participation. In. Delimatsis, P. Bijlmakers S. & Borowicz, M. *The Evolution of Transnational Rule-makers through Crises*. Cambridge University Press.
- › Contreras, J. L. (2019). Understanding 'Balance' Requirements for Standards Development Organizations. *CPI Antitrust Chronicle*, (2).
- › Delimatsis, P., Kanevskaia, O., & Verghese, Z. (2021). Strategic behavior in standards development organizations in times of crisis. *Tex. Intell. Prop. LJ*, 29, 127.
- › Kanevskaia, O. (2017). Governance within standards development organizations: WHO owns the game. In 2017 ITU Kaleidoscope: Challenges for a Data-Driven Society (ITU K) (pp. 1-8). IEEE.
- › Murphy, C., & Yates, J. (2013). The International Organization for Standardisation: Global Governance through Voluntary Consensus. *Business Regulation and Non-State Actors: Whose Standards Whose Development*, 81–94. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203126929-15>.
- › Tsilikas, H. (2022). Applying Antitrust to Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) – A Two-Sided Market Framework for Assessing SDO Governance. *Available at SSRN 4072541*.

Other sources on Standards Setting Organizations (SSOs):

- › Baron, J., & Spulber, D. F. (2018). Technology Standards and Standard Setting Organizations: Introduction to the Searle Center Database. *Journal of Economics and Management Strategy*, 27(3), 462–503. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jems.12257>.
- › Blind, K., Lorenz, A., & Rauber, J. (2020). Drivers for companies' entry into standard-setting organizations. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 68(1), 33-44.
- › Fiedler, C., Larrain, M., & Prüfer, J. (2023). Membership, governance, and lobbying in standard-setting organizations. *Research Policy*, 52(6), 104761.
- › Harcourt, A., Christou, G., & Simpson, S. (2020). *Global standard setting in internet governance*. Oxford University Press
- › Spulber, D. F. (2019). Standard setting organizations and standard essential patents: Voting and markets. *The Economic Journal*, 129(619), 1477-1509.
- › Valticos, N. (1996). Fifty years of standard-setting activities by the international labour organization. *Int'l Lab. Rev.*, 135, 393.
- › Wiegmann, P. M., Eggers, F., de Vries, H. J., & Blind, K. (2022). Competing Standard-Setting Organizations: A Choice Experiment. *Research Policy*, 51(2), 104427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2021.104427>.

Other sources on National Standards Bodies (NSBs):

- › Aletta, F., Xiao, J., & Kang, J. (2024). Identifying barriers to engage with soundscape standards: Insights from national standards bodies and experts. *JASA Express Letters*, 4(4).
- › De Vries, H. J., Manders, B., & Veurink, J. (2014). Cooperation between national standards bodies and universities. *Rotterdam: Rotterdam School of Management, Erasmus University*.
- › Gabriel, L. C. (2022). Supporting National Standards.
- › Gabriel, L. C., de Vries, H. J., & Cleeland, B. (2022). Stimulating Education about Standardisation – Activities and perspectives of National Standards Bodies. *Journal of Standardisation*, 1.
- › Song, Z., & Wang, X. (2018, October). Study on the Internationalization of Standards Bodies: Based on the Strategy Evolution of BSI. In *2018 9th International Conference on Information Technology in Medicine and Education (ITME)* (pp. 1037-1043). IEEE.
- › Wakke, P. (2010). Explanatory Factors for Service Standardisation at National Standards Bodies: Empirical Evidence at Sector Level. In *Paper for the EURAS Conference*.

4.2. Topic: Consortia-based Standardisation

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Today, processes between SSOs may differ quite considerably, and each one has its strengths and weaknesses. For instance, ‘speed’ does not come for free; it may lead to processes that may, for example, sacrifice a reasonable level of consensus for it or may be hijacked by personal or corporate interests. Coordination of SSOs working on similar (or virtually identical) technologies or on systems that depend on each other remains to be an issue. The wide range of coordination mechanisms that are available today helps, but it also serves to make the standards-setting environment more complex. A problem that persists in Europe until today is the perception of privately run standards consortia as being inferior to the formal ESO, in terms of processes, legitimacy of the output and inclusiveness. While this may be correct in theory, in practice these distinctions become increasingly blurred.

The ILOs examples: K6.1 K7.1

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Egyedi, T. M., & Koppenhol, A. (2010). The Standards War Between ODF and OOXML: Does Competition Between Overlapping ISO Standards Lead to Innovation? *International Journal of IT Standards and Standardisation Research (IJITSR)*, 8(1), 14. <https://www.igi-global.com/article/standards-war-between-odf-ooxml/39086>.
2. Van de Kaa (2009). Standards Battles for Complex Systems Empirical Research on the Home Network. Erasmus Research Institute Management (ERIM). Case Study: USB vs. Firewire, pp. 16, available at: <https://repub.eur.nl/pub/16011/EPS2009166ORG9058922052vdKaa.pdf>.

3. Case Study: The HD-DVD vs. Blu-Ray Disc:

<https://www.techhive.com/article/601489/timeline-hd-dvd-vs-blu-ray-disc.html>

Good practice:

Educators addressing consortia-based standardisation focus on its collaborative nature, where companies, industry groups, and stakeholders join forces to develop standards outside formal standards organizations.

Educators use various examples (e.g., OASIS, W3C, Wi-Fi Alliance, the Bluetooth Special Interest Group (SIG)) to show why this type of standardisation is usual in rapidly involving industries, e.g., information technology. They also use various examples to explain the effectiveness and efficiency of consortia-based standardisation, which is why it enables stakeholders to respond quickly to technological advancements and market needs. Through group discussions, they also discuss challenges, including limited global reach and standards battles. Case studies and role-playing exercises allow students to simulate the decision-making processes in consortia.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/consortia-based-standardisation>
- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition, Chapter 3.

Other sources on consortia-based standardisation:

- › Baron, J., Ménière, Y., & Pohlmann, T. (2014). Standards, consortia, and innovation. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*, 36, 22-35.
- › Choi, B., Raghu, T. S., Vinzé, A., & Dooley, K. J. (2019). Effectiveness of standards consortia: Social network perspectives. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 21, 405-416.
- › Egyedi, T. M. (2001). Beyond Consortia, Beyond Standardisation. New Case Material and Policy Threads. Final Report for the European Commission. Delft. The Netherlands.
- › Egyedi, T. M.; Koppenhol, A. (2010). The standards war between ODF and OOXML: Does competition between overlapping ISO standards lead to innovation? *International Journal of IT Standards and Standardisation Research (IJITSR)*, 8(1), 49-62.
- › Kherrazi, S. (2022). Exploring taxonomies and governance challenges of sponsored R&D consortia: Evidence from the EU framework program. *Journal of Innovation Economics & Management*, XXXIII.
- › Hesser, I. W. (2011). Standards Consortia.
- › Weiss, M., & Cargill, C. (1992). Consortia in the Standards Development Process. *Journal of the American society for information science*, 43(8), 559-565.
- › Teubner, L. K., Henkel, J., & Bekkers, R. (2021). Industry consortia in mobile telecommunications standards setting: Purpose, organization and diversity. *Telecommunications Policy*, 45(3), 102059.

4.3. Topic: Company Standardisation

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Company standardisation is standardisation within a company, including positioning towards external standardisation (Simons & De Vries, 2002). Company standardisation mainly covers three aspects - developing standards to be used only internally (within the company), developing standards to be used externally and developing standards to become sectoral or industrial standards (De Vries, 1999). The interplay of companies and standardisation can be various. Companies can be direct users of standards;

they can passively or actively participate in standards development using different mechanisms of standardisation or doing both. In formal organizations for standardisation, companies can decide their level of involvement - to be represented by experts in NSBs and European or international organizations for standardisation: to comment and vote on national, European or international draft standards; to actively participate in shaping national, European and international standards; to actively develop national, European and international standards; to chair a technical committee (with the support of secretarial management of SDOs) or working groups (WGs) and coordinate the work of TCs with their respective subordinate TCs or WGs, and propose new standardisation projects.⁷ The level of involvement in standardisation is a strategic decision of the company. Some consortia or alliances do not accept observers or passive participants who do not contribute to the development or agreements about a solution or agree to use a solution. Standardisation is an activity that directly influences market advantages and business strategies. To expand the market for their products or services, some companies impose their solution on their counterparts in the global or regional markets and suggest it becomes standard. It might be a common technological platform or solution with a higher level of generality, which enables the interoperability of different devices and software modules and enhances the compatibility of products and their components. At the same time, core technologies or other functionalities might be kept a business secret. For some companies, it is “a nonmarket strategy, in which a company creates a business environment that is advantageous to them by engaging other companies with a clear intention to convince them that the company’s technology has potential for the common good”.⁸ Companies with a more considerable influence on standard setting can reduce the time needed to modify products and adjust to standard changes in advance, thus introducing new products to the market more quickly (Wen et al., 2020).

The ILOs examples: TBD

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Case Study: IKEA’s IWAY Supplier Code of Conduct

<https://www.ikea.com/global/en/our-business/how-we-work/iway-our-supplier-code-of-conduct/>

Good practice:

Educators introducing students to company standardisation emphasize why companies develop standards, e.g., to ensure quality and safety, enhance efficiency, and maintain consistency of their business operations. They use examples of company standards developed within different industries and sectors which often align with international and national standards while, at the same time, being tailored to specific company’s needs. Educators may also include a simulation game or interactive workshop aimed at drafting a company standard or analysing the alignment of company standards with external frameworks (e.g., industry-specific standards).

Recommended sources:

⁷ See more at www.snv.ch/en/.

⁸ Standardisation is the key to future business growth, allowing to seize the market advantage and providing a basis of decision-making for business strategies, see more at <https://www.sony-semicon.com/en/feature/2022031801.html>.

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/company-standardisation>

Other sources on company standardisation:

- › Blind, K., & Müller, J.-A. (2020). Why corporate groups care about company standards. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(11), 3399–3414.
- › Clarke, C. (2006). *Automotive Production Systems and Standardisation: From Ford to the Case of Mercedes-Benz*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- › de Vries, H. J. (1999). *Standardisation: A Business Approach to the Role of National Standardisation Organizations*. Springer Science+Business Media, LLC.
<https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9780792386384>.
- › Hesser, W. (2010). Standardisation within a Company: Strategic Perspective. In W. Hesser, A. Feilzer, & H. de Vries (Eds.), *Standardisation in Companies and Markets* (3rd ed., p. 569). Druckerei Helmut Schmidt University., pp. 221.
- › Slob, F. J., & de Vries, H. J. (2002). Best practice in company standardisation. Available at SSRN 371029.
- › Sorte, W. F. (2014). Standardisation for Incremental Innovation: A Case Study in the Brazilian Automobile Industry. *International Journal of Lean Enterprise Research*, 1(1), 81-93.

5. How standards are developed (basics)?

5.1. Topic: How standards are developed within SDOs in Europe?

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The new EU Strategy on Standardisation (2022) aims to enable resilient, green, and digital strengthening of the EU single market (Radauer et al., 2022). The new EU Strategy sets up a series of actions such as prioritizing and addressing standardisation needs in strategic areas, improving the governance and integrity of the European standardisation system, enhancing European leadership in global standards, supporting innovation, and enabling the next generation of standardisation experts. The European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC) develop European Standards (ENs) and other publications, including Technical Specifications (TSs), Technical Reports (TRs), Workshop Agreements (CWAs), and Guides; while the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) develops European Standards (ENs), ETSI Standards (ESs), ETSI Guides (EGs), ETSI Technical Specifications (TSs), ETSI Technical Reports (TRs), ETSI Special Reports (SRs), ETSI Group Specifications (GSs), and ETSI Group Reports (GRs).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.2., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3., and S6.6. toward S7.6. and S7.11.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Serious Game: Knights of KANelot (KAN)

Keywords: Standardisation, Standards

About: Knights of KANelot (KAN) can be played as a board game and online. The objective of the game is to learn the process of European standardisation. The „boring“ process details are explained with funny storytelling. Storyline: It's a hard life for a knight. His helmet doesn't fit properly, the visor is broken – again – and the helmet is also starting to rust. Wouldn't it be nice for knights to have a safe helmet that is comfortable and functional? The OSH knights of KANelot have an idea: what we need is a standard. And so off they go, with other knights and ladies, to create a European standard.

Details:

- › Time to play: Ca. 30 min per round (depending on reading speed)
- › Languages: English, German
- › Target group: beginners
- › Group size: Up to 6 players per board; online any.

Contact and online version: www.kan.de/en/publications/kanelot-the-game

2. Serious Game: BSI level 3 (in development)

Keywords: Standardisation, Standards

About: This process-based board game focuses on the exchange of best practices among experts. The game introduces the main steps of a BSI standardisation process along with key terms used by standards organizations during development.

Details:

- › Time to play: 60-90 minutes.
- › Target group: Rudimentary prior standardisation knowledge
- › Group size: 3-5 players per group.

Contact: magnus.hakvag@hoknowledge.com

Background:

Developed with and for the British Standards Institution (BSI) to engage young professionals in using standards and partaking in standardisation work.

3. Serious Game: Seriously Standard Game

Keywords: Standards, standardisation, market access

About: This game takes the player through a simplified standardisation process (CEN), with a clear narrative focus on the business benefits of participation. The game introduces and explains some key terms of standardisation and demonstrates how different levels of participation can lead to more and less favourable outcomes. The game also demonstrates the give-and-take of standardisation, showing that a business cannot get a standard moulded to their every need – but may be able to exert some influence and, importantly, be informed on things to come (e.g., new requirements).

Details:

- › Time to play: 60 minutes.
- › Target group: Organizations that have no or limited experience with standardisation
- › Group size: 3-5 players per group.

Contact: magnus.hakvag@hoknowledge.com

Background: Developed for Standards Norway.

Good practice:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/how-standards-are-developed-within-sdos-europe>
- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition, Chapter 3.

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › CEN/CENELEC. (2022). European standards. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/european-standardisation/european-standards/>.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2022). CEN/CENELEC Internal Regulations – Part 2, Common Rules for Standardisation Work, Brussels – Belgium, Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: https://boss.cen.eu/media/BOSS%20CENELEC/ref/ir2_e.pdf.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2022). CEN/CENELEC Internal Regulations – Part 3, Principles and rules for the structure and Drafting of CEN and CENELEC documents (ISO/IEC Directives – Part 2:2021). Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: https://boss.cen.eu/media/BOSS%20CENELEC/ref/ir3_e.pdf.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2020), CEN- CENELEC Guide 29 – CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreements – A rapid way to standardisation. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/Guides/CEN-CLC/cenclcguid29.pdf>.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2021). Flexible standards development process. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: https://boss.cen.eu/media/BOSS%20CEN/ref/flex_process_operational.pdf.
- › CEN. (2022). CEN Deliverables ppt. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://boss.cen.eu/reference-material/guidancedoc/pages/del/>.
- › CEN. (2022a). Developing deliverables. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://boss.cen.eu/developingdeliverables/pages/en/pages/>.
- › CEN. (2022b). Main steps of development for each CEN deliverable. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: https://boss.cen.eu/media/CEN/ref/cen_deliverables_table1.pdf.
- › CEN. (2022c). Designation system for CEN deliverables. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: https://boss.cen.eu/media/CEN/ref/cen_deliverables_table1.pdf.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2022b). European standards. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/european-standardisation/european-standards/>.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2022c). Internal Regulations Part 2, Common Rules for Standardisation Work, Brussels – Belgium, Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: https://boss.cen.eu/media/BOSS%20CENELEC/ref/ir2_e.pdf.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2022d). CEN/CENELEC Internal Regulations – Part 3, Principles and rules for the structure and Drafting of CEN and CENELEC documents (ISO/IEC Directives – Part 2:2021, modified). Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: https://boss.cen.eu/media/BOSS%20CENELEC/ref/ir3_e.pdf.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2022e). Brochure - Standards: catalyst for innovation. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: https://www.standardsplusinnovation.eu/_files/ugd/b28c29_482fa9c0cba24d86a0bd3b8c5bd705f5.pdf.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2022f). Brochure - Catalyzing standardisation in R&I projects. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: https://www.standardsplusinnovation.eu/_files/ugd/8442a0_e295c1d118ed457485c58c3a199dc469.pdf.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2020a). CEN/CENELEC Guide 23 – Research consortium bridge – Addressing research and innovation in European standardisation activities and deliverables. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/Guides/CEN-CLC/cenclcguid23.pdf>.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2020b), CEN- CENELEC Guide 29 – CEN/CENELEC workshop agreements – A rapid way to standardisation. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/Guides/CEN-CLC/cenclcguid29.pdf>.

- › CEN/CENELEC. (2021). Flexible standards development process. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: https://boss.cen.eu/media/BOSS%20CEN/ref/flex_process_operational.pdf.
- › CEN/CENELEC. (2022a). CEN Guides flowchart. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/european-standardisation/european-standards/types-of-deliverables/>.
- › Egan, M. (2024). Navigating transatlantic power dynamics in ICT standardisation – The case of ETSI. *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13511610.2024.2321842>.
- › European Commission. (2022). An EU Strategy on Standardisation – Setting global standards in support of a resilient, green and digital EU single market. Brussels.
- › Radauer, A., Baronowski, S., Yeghyan, M., et al. (2022), Scoping study for supporting the development of a code of practice for researchers on standardisation: final report, Tardos, G.(editor), European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/567608>
- › ISO, & CEN. (2016). Vienna Agreement. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://isotc.iso.org/livelink/livelink/fetch/2000/2122/3146825/4229629/4230450/4230458/customview.html?func=ll&objId=4230458&objAction=browse&sort=subtype>.

5.2. Topic: How standards are developed within SDOs internationally?

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The International Organization for Standardisation (ISO) is an organization that develops International Standards (ISs) and other deliverables, such as ISO Technical Specifications (ISO/Ts), ISO Technical Reports (ISO/TRs), ISO Publicly Available Specifications (ISO/PASs), International Workshop Agreements (IWAs), and ISO Guides (ISO/IEC 2022). ISO distinguishes the normative and the informative deliverables regarding what their content includes (ISO, 2019c). International Standards (ISs), ISO Technical Specifications (ISO/Ts), and ISO Publicly Available Specifications (ISO/PASs) are normative deliverables, ISO Technical Reports (ISO/TRs) are informative deliverables, and International Workshop Agreements (IWAs) and ISO Guides do not fit into these categories. The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) develops its deliverables for specific electrical, electronic, and information technology areas. Besides International Standards (ISs), IEC deliverables are IEC Technical Specifications (IEC/Ts), IEC Technical Reports (IEC/TRs), IEC Publicly Available Specifications (IEC/PASs), IEC Guides, IEC Amendments, IEC Systems Reference Deliverables, IEC Technical Corrigenda, and IEC Interpretation Sheets.

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.2., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3., and S6.6. toward S7.6. and S7.11.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Serious Game (ISO)

Keywords: Standards, Standardisation, diversity, inclusion

About: This game, developed for and with ISO, features standards and standardisation, and specifically how inclusion and diversity apply to standardisation work. Players are presented with short scenarios, by drawing cards related to the

topic which they must relate to, discussing and suggesting actions to handle problems. The game uses tokens to present information needed for play but still requires player discussion to sort through the information, extract what is relevant, and put it onto the game board in a logical, meaningful order. In this game, the players themselves, rather than the game artefact, are largely responsible for learning, as it relies on

players having experience with and knowledge about the topic at hand. Furthermore, if possible, players should be placed in nationally and culturally diverse groups to promote the sharing of different perspectives, and subsequent learning from seeing a familiar topic through a new lens. This lets players jointly discover each other's ways of understanding the world. As such, the game focuses on reflecting on own, existing practices and perspectives (i.e., applications of theory and knowledge) in light of others' practices and perspectives.

Details:

- › Time to play: 60-90 minutes.
- › Target group: Industry experts and practitioners
- › Group size: 3-5 players per group.

Contact: magnus.hakvag@hoknowledge.com

Background: Developed with and for ISO, for use in their 2022 Annual Meeting

Good practice:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/how-standards-are-developed-within-sdos-internationally>
- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition, Chapter 3.

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › Delimatsis, P. (2018). Global Standard-Setting 2.0: How the WTO Spotlights ISO and Impacts the Transnational Standard-Setting Process. *Duke Journal of Comparative & International Law*, 28, 273-326 <https://scholarship.law.duke.edu/djcil/vol28/iss2/3>.
- › Delimatsis P. (2015). *The Law, Economics and Politics of International Standardisation*. Cambridge University Press.
- › European Commission. (2022). An EU Strategy on Standardisation – Setting global standards in support of a resilient, green and digital EU single market. Brussels.
- › ISO. (2016). Model document of an International Standard - Rice model. Accessed on January 26, 2023. Retrieved from: https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/developing_standards/docs/en/model_document-rice_model.pdf.

- › ISO. (2016a). How to write standards – tips for standards writers. Accessed on January 26, 2023. Retrieved from:
https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/developing_standards/docs/en/how-to-write-standards.pdf.
- › ISO. (2019). ISO training. ISO deliverables. Accessed on January 26, 2023. Retrieved from:
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KA2. Standardisation Interdependencies and Roles in Specific Contexts

6. European System of Standardisation

6.1. Topic: European System of Standardisation

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The European Standardisation System has an important role in establishing and strengthening the European Single Market. It is a unique standardisation system in the world, primarily because once published, the European Standard becomes the national standard in the 34 European countries, which enables the free circulation of services and products, facilitating cross-border trade – within Europe and the rest of the world

(CEN/CENELEC, 2023). European standards are developed by European Standardisation Organizations (ESOs) (EC, 2023a): the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC), and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI). The European standard is defined as „a standard adopted by a European standardisation organization“ (EC, 2023a). The European standardisation framework provided by CEN/CENELEC is based on having a single European standard implemented identically throughout the member countries with the obligation of withdrawing any conflicting national standards, and no new work can start on issues covered by European standards (CEN/CENELEC, 2015).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.2., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3., S6.2., S6.4., S6.6., S7.3., S7.11.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Good practice:

Educators highlight the role of the European standardisation system in promoting harmonization across the EU. They explore the relationship between European Standardisation Organizations (ESOs) and emphasize the role European harmonized standards play in facilitating the free movement of goods, enhancing safety, and ensuring environmental protection while supporting policies and legislation within the EU single market. Educators often use examples to show how the application of European harmonized standards demonstrates compliance with EU directives (following the New Approach to Technical Harmonization and Standardisation).

Recommended sources:

- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition, Chapter 3.

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Other sources on the European Standards:

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- › Kamara, I. (forthcoming in 2025). *Standardizing personal data protection*. (1 ed.) Oxford University Press.
- › Manatos, M. J., & Huisman, J. (2020). The use of the European Standards and Guidelines by national accreditation agencies and local review panels. *Quality in higher education*, 26(1), 48-65.
- › Orviska, M., Nemeč, J., & Hudson, J. (2013). Standardisation and the European standards organizations. *Central European Journal of Public Policy*, 7(2), 36-58.
- › van Deventer, O., Spethmann, N., Loeffler, M., Amoretti, M., van den Brink, R., Bruno, N., ... & Wilhelm-Mauch, F. K. (2022). Towards European standards for quantum technologies. *EPJ Quantum Technology*, 9(1), 33.

Other sources on the Harmonized Standards:

- › Colombo, C., & Eliantonio, M. (2017). Harmonized technical standards as part of EU law: Juridification with a number of unresolved legitimacy concerns? Case C-613/14 James Elliot Construction Limited v. Irish Asphalt Limited, EU: C: 2016: 821. *Maastricht Journal of European and Comparative Law*, 24(2), 323-340.
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Other sources on the Product Compliance and Presumption of Conformity:

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- › Maskus, K. E., Otsuki, T., & Wilson, J. S. (2005). The cost of compliance with product standards for firms in developing countries: An econometric study (Vol. 3590). World Bank Publications.
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- › Twigg-Flesner, C. (2020). Conformity of goods and digital content/digital services. *El Derecho privado en el nuevo paradigma digital*, Barcelona-Madrid, Marcial Pons.

Other sources relevant to the topic:

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- › European Commission. (2022). The 'Blue Guide' on the implementation of EU product rules 2022. Accessed on February 7, 2023. Retrieved from: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv%3AOJ.C_.2022.247.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ%3AC%3A2022%3A247%3ATOC.
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- › Prifti, K., & Fosch-Villaronga, E. (2024). Towards Experimental Standardisation for AI governance in the EU. *Computer Law and Security Review*, 52, Article 105959.
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7. Interdependencies between Standardisation and Research

7.1. Topic: Interdependencies between Standardisation and Research

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The ILOs examples: TBD

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Good practice:

Recommended sources:

8. Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation

8.1. Topic: Interdependencies between Standardisation and Innovation

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Ideally, standards incorporate valuable and innovative ideas to represent the best technical solution to a problem. And the process of standardisation, in itself, can be a source of new innovative ideas as well. Hence, there are interesting interdependencies between standardisation and innovation. At the same time, some might have the feeling that standardisation and innovation are also opposites" (Perera, 2010), because the first appears to be about keeping things the same, whereas the second is about the development of new things. Firstly, there is the relationship between research and standardisation. While research at universities creates knowledge at the frontiers of knowledge and has the potential to create significant and independent contributions to standardisation (being a form of knowledge valorization), it is not easy to make this knowledge transfer channel work to its best extent (Bekkers et al., 2006) so stakeholders, such as the European Commission are investigating ways how the outcomes of publicly funded research and innovation (R&I) projects can be brought into standardisation (EC, 2023b). Economists are also conducting econometric work on 'standard-relevant publications', aiming to understand which scientific results are actually utilized in standards (Blind & Fenton, 2022). Secondly, there is a relationship between economic growth, trade, and standardisation. When standards perform roles, such as reducing variety, codifying knowledge, and offering compatibility, among other things, they create economic effects

such as economies of scale, network effects, and reduction of transaction costs, which affect trade as well as wealth and welfare (Swann, 2010a). Standards can remove trade barriers and promote open markets but can also act as inhibitors and limit access to national markets. The development, use and national adoption of standards can create strategic advantages on the global market: empirical studies suggest that the national level of adoption of both national and international standards has a positive effect on export, whereas the effects on import are mixed (Swann, 2010b). The uneven distribution of ownership of Standard Essential Patents (SEPs, see below) across the globe creates ‘have-not’ countries (Contreras, 2016). Standardisation can also contribute to economic growth as a whole (Blind et al., 2011), even though isolating the exact extent of that contribution is difficult. Finally, there is a relationship between intellectual property rights (IPRs) and standardisation. Especially anticipatory standards seek to include the most innovative ideas to meet challenging design requirements and expectations for the new standard, but those that create such innovative ideas often patent them. Over the years, SDOs have developed policies for patents in standards. IETF and W3C (the key standards bodies for internet standards) avoid the inclusion of patented technologies unless it is guaranteed that royalty-free licenses are available to any implementer. Many other standards bodies, such as ISO, IEC, CEN, CENELEC, and ETSI, adopted a policy where patent owners are allowed to request monetary licenses for patents that are required to implement the standards (Standard-Essential Patents – SEPs), but the owners must commit themselves that these licenses are available under Fair, Reasonable, and Non-Discriminatory (FRAND) conditions. Even with these frameworks in place, SEPs have remained an area in which disputes occur, and we see both court cases as well as policy interventions (Maskus et al., 2013). In 2023, the European Commission proposed the ‘Essentiality’ Regulation, which introduces, inter alia, a public system that provides transparency on which precise patents are essential to technical standards (Bekkers et al., 2022).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K7.1., S6.6., S7.2., S7.3., S7.7., S7.8., S7.11.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Serious Game: The World of Standardisation (DIN)

Keywords: Standardisation & Innovations

About: The World of Standardisation (DIN) is interactive board game with objective to develop a strategic understanding about standardisation in innovation context. Storyline: Congrats, for you innovation you won the Innovation Trophy! It comes with some time and money. The game offers different choices: patent, standard national/ European/ international, specifications; and combinations are possible. Decisions to be made within the team. The game provides real-life-inspired standardisation situations, and it is designed to inspire questions.

Details:

- › Time to play: according to decisions Ca. 30 min per round.
- › Group size: played in teams of 2-5, max. 2 teams per board.
- › Target group: students, founders
- › Languages: English, German

Contact: amelie.leipprand@din.de

2. Serious Smiley Game (UoB, HSbooster.eu)

Keywords: Standardisation & researchers

About: The Serious Smiley Game is a role-play and simulation game that aims to develop soft skills needed in standardisation processes, focusing on argumentation skills, common understanding and strategic positioning. Furthermore, it emphasizes the role of a researcher with innovative ideas in a standardisation context. It is a facilitated game based on careful instructions to provoke communication among the game participants and increase their understanding of the process of reaching a common understanding, which is the first and primary step for achieving a common agreement. The Serious Smiley Game is publicly available and can be played at professional training or university classes.

Details:

- › Time to play: 60 to 90 minutes
- › Group size: played in teams of 5, one facilitator can facilitate up to 6 teams (30 persons)
- › Target group: students (simplified version), researchers, standardisation professionals
- › Languages: English, Serbian.

Background: The first version of this game was developed in 2015 by [Professor Ivana Mijatovic](#). Since then, the game has been played regularly in the Standardisation course of bachelor studies at the Faculty of Organizational Sciences, University of Belgrade. For the [HSBooster.eu Training Academy](#), this game has been improved and tested on different sites. The experiences are positive. We thank [Magnus Hakvag](#), CEO of the House of Knowledge, who gave us valuable advice and suggestions and thus contributed to improving this game

Contact: ivana.mijatovic@fon.bg.ac.rs

3. Serious IP Game

Keywords: IP, IPR, SEP, Innovation

About: This game is a dilemma game where the players will have to choose different countermeasures on different incidents and related to agreed long-term goals related to the WIPO global innovation index. In the game, the teamwork on how to improve a country's innovation performance as measured by GII. In this particular edition, the players relate to SEP and how to improve Norway's score.

Details:

- › Time to play: This game can be completed in 1 to 5 hours, depending on the team/time.
- › Group size: 3-5 players per group.
- › Target group: Organizations or teams broadly

Contact: magnus.hakvag@hoknowledge.com

4. Serious Game: SIT Edition

Keywords: IP, IPR, Standards, Innovation

About: In this game the players will have to relate to the most relevant inputs, facts and incidents about Innovation, Standards, IP and IPR and how this is part of a company's different policies. During game play the teams have as a team, with inputs from facilitator produced solutions to the most common challenges any type of organization will meet in, innovation, IP and standards and jointly created policies.

Details:

- › Time to play: This game can be completed in 2 to 4 hours, depending on the team/time.
- › Target group: Organizations or teams broadly
- › Group size: 3-5 players per group.

Contact: magnus.hakvag@hoknowledge.com

Background: <https://vimeo.com/172708694>

5. Serious Game: War Room

Keywords: IP, IPR, Strategy

Standardisation is part of decision-making and activities but not the main focus.

About: This game links IP, IPR, business development, standards, innovation, and competitiveness with business strategy using our IP and Competitiveness Canvas. Players are presented with a case to analyze by assessing and evaluating available information. Game cards are used to present information, from which players extract relevant details, make decisions, and set up a strategy. The team is then exposed to several happenings they must relate to, to see if their strategy "holds water", and consider what they could have done differently.

Details:

- › Time to play: This game can be completed in 1,5 to 4 hours, depending on the team.
- › Target group: Organizations or teams broadly
- › Group size: 3-5 players per group.

Contact: magnus.hakvag@hoknowledge.com

Background: <https://vimeo.com/223297825>

Gameplay from TU-Berlin with Master students

6. Serious Game: War Room Corporate

Keywords: IP, IPR, Strategy

Standardisation is part of decision-making and activities but not the main focus.

About: Similar game to War-room, where we follow the company from War-room when the company has become a big corporate dealing with standards, SEP and Transfer pricing. This game links IP, IPR, business development, standards, innovation, and competitiveness with business strategy using our IP and Competitiveness Canvas. Players are presented with a case to analyze by assessing and evaluating available information. Game cards are used to present information, from which players extract relevant details, make decisions, and set up a strategy. The team is then exposed to several happenings they must relate to, to see if their strategy “holds water”, and consider what they could have done differently.

Details:

- › Time to play: This game can be completed in 2 to 4 hours, depending on the team.
- › Target group: Organizations or teams broadly
- › Group size: 3-5 players per group.

Contact: magnus.hakvag@hoknowledge.com

7. Serious IP-Department Game (CEIPI)

Keywords: Management system, IP, IPR, Innovation

Standardisation part of decision-making and activities but not main focus.

About: The Serious IP-Department Game is created in cooperation with CEIPI, University of Strasbourg. The Serious IP-Department Game is designed to create an engaging, facilitated exchange of experience and knowledge. Play happens in groups of 3-5 where the centrepiece of the game is an IP-department canvas, which is used to structure and evaluate relevant information (presented on playing cards), reveal

interrelations, and support discussion. The game was played digitally by the MIPLM class, but it can also be played on-site with a physical game.

Contact: magnus.hakvag@hoknowledge.com

Background: <https://ipbusinessacademy.org/a-serious-ip-department-game-5th-module-miplm>

Good practice:

Educators may use the Serious Smiley Game to develop soft skills needed in the standardisation process, such as argumentation skills, common understanding, and strategic positioning.

Recommended sources:

- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice. ETSI (Vol. 2). (especially, Chapter 5 on standardisation and innovation, Section 5.3 on standardisation and research, and Chapter 7 on standardisation and IPR).
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- › Hawkins (ed.) Handbook of Standards and Innovation. Edward Elgar Publishing. DOI: 10.4337/9781783470082.

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › Baron, J., Spulber, D.F. (2018). Technology Standards and Standard Setting Organizations: Introduction to the Searle Center Database. *Journal of Economics and Management Strategy*, 27(3), pp. 462–503
- › Bekkers, R., & Updegrove, A. (2013). A study of IPR policies and practices of a representative group of Standards Setting Organizations worldwide. Updated version. Washington, DC: National Academies of Science. Available at http://www.nap.edu/catalog.php?record_id=18510
- › Bekkers, R., Blind, K., Coenen, H., Iverson, E. Jacobs, K., Hossain, K. (2006). Case studies on the interface between research and standardisation, and case studies on patent pools as a coordination mechanism. Project co-funded by the
- › European Commission within the Sixth Framework Programme, STREP, Priority 8, Contract 503 594.
- › Bekkers, R., Duysters, G. & Verspagen, B. (2002). Intellectual property rights, strategic technology agreements and market structure: The case of GSM. In: *Research Policy* 31(7) 141-1161. DOI: 10.1016/S0048-7333(01)00189-5.

- › Bekkers, R., Henkel, J., Tur, E.M., Vorst, T. v.d., Driesse, M., Kang, B., Martinelli, A., Maas, W., Nijhof, B., Raiteri, E., Teubner, L. (2020). Pilot study for essentiality assessment of Standard Essential Patents, Thumm, N. editor(s), EUR 30111 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, JRC119894, doi:10.2760/68906, ISBN 978-92-76-16666-5.
- › Bekkers, R., Tur, Elena M., Henkel, Joachim, Vorst, Tommy van der, Driesse, Menno, Contreras, Jorge L. (2022). Overcoming inefficiencies in patent licensing: A method to assess patent essentiality for technical standards. *Research Policy* 51(10). DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2022.104590.
- › Blind, K., Baldan, F., Tardos, G., Kromer, L. et al., (2024). European standardisation panel survey – Final report, Baldan, F., Tardos, G. editor(s). Publications Office of the European Union, ISBN 978-92-68-12065-1, doi:10.2777/643814.
- › Blind, K., Gauch, S. (2009): Research and standardisation in nanotechnology: Evidence from Germany. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 34(3), 320–342.
- › Blind, K., Fenton, A. (2022). Standard-relevant publications: evidence, processes and influencing factors. *Scientometrics* (2022) 127:577–602. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-021-04210-8.
- › Blind, K., Jungmittag, A., & Mangelsdorf, A. (2011). *The Economic Benefits of Standardisation: An update of the study carried out by DIN in 2000*. Berlin: DIN. <https://www.din.de/resource/blob/89552/68849fab0eeeeafb56c5a3ffee9959c5/economic-benefits-of-standardisation-en-data.pdf>.
- › Blind, K., Kenney, M., Leiponen, A., Simcoe, T. (2023). Standards and innovation: A review and introduction to the special issue. *Research Policy*, Vol. 52(8), pp. 104830. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2023.104830.
- › Blind, K. Thumm, N. (2004). Interrelation between patenting and standardisation strategies: Empirical evidence and policy implications. *Research Policy*, 33(10), pp. 1583–1598.
- › Contreras, J.L., (2016). Patents, standards and Borders. Workshop on Mega-Regionalism: New Challenges for Trade and Innovation (MCTI) Honolulu, Hawaii, USA, January 20-21, 2016.
- › Contreras, J.L., 2019. Technical standards, standards-setting organizations and intellectual property: A survey of the literature (with an emphasis on empirical approaches). In: Depoorter, B., Menell, P., Schwartz, D. (Eds.), *Research Handbook on the Economics of Intellectual Property Law, Vol 2 – Analytical Methods*. Edward Elgar, Cheltenham and Northampton, pp. 185–235. DOI: 10.4337/9781789903997.
- › European Commission (2023). REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on Standard Essential Patents and Amending Regulation (EU)2017/1001 COM (2023) 232 final.
- › ISO. (2022). Standards and innovation – What does the research say? <https://www.iso.org/publication/PUB100466.html>.
- › Leiponen, A.E. (2008). Competing through cooperation: The organization of standard setting in wireless telecommunications. *Management Science*, 2008, 54(11), pp. 1904–1919. DOI: 10.1287/mnsc.1080.0912.
- › Maskus, K., Bekkers, R., Block, M.S., Contreras, J., Gilbert, R. J., Goodman, D. J., Marasco, A., Simcoe, T., Smoot, O., Suttmeier, R., Updegrove, A. (2013). In Maskus, K., & Merrill, S. A. (Eds.). *Patent challenges for standard-setting in the global economy: Lessons from the ICT industry*. Committee on Intellectual Property Management in Standard-Setting Processes Board on Science, Technology, and Economic Policy, Policy and Global Affairs. National Research Council of the National Academies. Washington, D.C: The National Academies Press. DOI: 10.17226/18510; ISBN 978-0-309-29312-9.
- › Perera, C. (2010). Standardisation and Innovation. In W. Hesser, A. J. Feilzer, & H. J. de Vries (Eds.), *Standardisation in companies and markets (3rd ed., pp. 403–442)*. Hamburg, Rotterdam: Helmut-Schmidt- Universität; Erasmus University of Rotterdam.

- › Rysman, M., Simcoe, T. (2008). Patents and the performance of voluntary standard-setting organizations. *Management Science* 54(11), pp. 1920–1934. DOI: 10.1287/mnsc.1080.0919.
- › Swann, G. M. P. (2010a). International Standards and Trade: A Review of the Empirical Literature. *OECD Trade Policy Working Papers*, No. 97, OECD Publishing. DOI:10.1787/18166873.
- › Swann, G. M. P. (2010b). The Economics of Standardisation: An Update. Report for the UK Department of Business, Innovation and Skills (BIS). <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a790abd40f0b679c0a0812d/10-1135-economics-of-standardisation-update.pdf>.
- › Blind, K. (2009). Standardisation: a catalyst for innovation. Inaugural lecture at Erasmus University Rotterdam, available from <http://hdl.handle.net/1765/17558>
- › Blind, K., Gauch, S. (2009). Research and standardisation in nanotechnology: evidence from Germany. *The Journal of Technology Transfer* 34(3), 320-342
- › Wiegmann, P.M. (2019). *Managing Innovation and Standards: A Case in the European Heating Industry*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-01532-9>

9. Interdependencies between Standards and Markets

9.1. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Markets

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

More than 80% of all goods on the market are produced in compliance with standards. Standards play an important role in the European Single Market. Without wide use of standards, the global market will not be possible. The relationship between standards and markets is two-way. Standards constitute markets, shape behavior on markets, define characteristics of markets and set the framework for standards, while markets generate demand for standards, create standards, define characteristics of the standards and shape mechanisms for standards development (Hesser et al., 2010, p. 458).

The ILOs examples: S5.2., S7.3., S7.7.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. The success of the ISO 9001 and other Management System Standards, which publication and further revisions were established global market of consulting services, certification and accreditation services is an example of how standards create markets (see more at the link: <https://dataintelo.com/report/iso-certification-market-report>).
2. Serious Edu4Standards game: Game in development as part of the Consortium

Keywords: standards, market assess and market control and values.

About: In this team-based game players will be the top management of a company that is going to enter the European inner market. They will analyze the market mechanisms before entering the market and relating

to the requirement and control “pyramid” (Regulations/laws vs governmental control. Standards vs Market control, Internal procedures vs internal control on the basis of European Values.

Details:

- › Time to play: This game can be completed in 1 to 3 hours, depending on the team/time.
- › Target group: Organizations or teams broadly
- › Group size: 3-5 players per group.

Background: Edu4standards.eu deliverables

Good practice:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Recommended sources:

- › Hesser W., Feilzer A., de Vries H., (Eds.), *Standardisation in Companies and Markets*, Helmut Schmidt University Germany, Erasmus University of Rotterdam, Netherlands.p.458
- › Blind, K. The economic functions of standards in the innovation process.
- › Hawkins, R., Page, R (Edt.). (2020). Handbook of Innovation and Standards.

9.2. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Trade

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The ILOs examples: TBD

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Good practice:

Recommended sources:

9.3. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Public Procurement

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The ILOs examples: TBD

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Good practice:

Recommended sources:

9.4. Topic: Interdependencies between Standards and Policy

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The ILOs examples: TBD

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Good practice:

Recommended sources:

9.5. Topic: Standards Battles

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Many markets are characterized by increasing returns to adoption which result in single de facto standards that are dominating. Sources of increasing returns include direct and indirect network effects. In these markets, standards battles are often fought. Scholars have focused on why certain standards dominate over other standards. They have come up with factors that affect standard dominance. Teachers who cover the de-facto standardisation process can teach students how firms can utilize strategies to set dominant standards. When firms apply these factors to the battles in which they participate, the uncertainty for firms with respect to the decision that they must make for which standard to choose will decrease.

The ILOs examples: S5.2., S7.3., S7.7.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. Case Studies:

- › Gallagher, S. R. (2012). The battle of the blue laser DVDs: The significance of corporate strategy in standards battles. *Technovation* 32(2): 90-98.
- › Van de Kaa, G., & H. De Vries (2015). Factors for winning format battles: A comparative case study. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change* 91(2): 222-235.
- › Van de Kaa, G., et al. (2015). Strategies in network industries: The importance of inter-organizational networks, complementary goods, and commitment. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management* 27(1): 73-86.

2. Teaching Game:

Video gaming platform wars:

<https://mitsloan.mit.edu/teaching-resources-library/platform-wars-simulating-battle-video-game-supremacy>

Good practice:

Students are interested in understanding the factors that affect standards dominance and thereby understanding the specifics of standards battles. In lectures, it is recommended to explain the factors by making use of the example case studies that were published in the literature and for each case study cover one or more factors that were relevant in that case. After these lectures, students like to play a game and apply the factors.

Recommended sources:

- › Schilling, M. A. (2020). Strategic management of technological innovation. New York, USA, McGraw-Hill.

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › David, P. A. (1985). "Clio and the economics of QWERTY." American Economic Review 75(2): 332-337.
- › Gallagher, S. R. and S. H. Park (2002). Innovation and competition in standard-based industries: A Historical Analysis of the U.S. Home Video Game Market. IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management 49(1): 67-82.
- › Schilling, M. A. (1998). Technological lockout: An integrative model of the economic and strategic factors driving technology success and failure. Academy of Management Review 23(2): 267-284.
- › Shapiro, C. and H. R. Varian (1998). Information rules, a strategic guide to the network economy. Boston, Massachusetts, Harvard Business School Press.
- › Suarez, F. F. (2004). "Battles for technological dominance: An integrative framework." Research Policy 33(2): 271-286.
- › Van de Kaa, G. and H. De Vries (2015). "Factors for winning format battles: A comparative case study." Technological Forecasting & Social Change 91(2): 222-235.
- › Van de Kaa, G., et al. (2011). "Factors for winning interface format battles: A review and synthesis of the literature." Technological Forecasting & Social Change 78(8): 1397-1411.

10. Legal Aspects of Standardisation

10.1. Topic: Legal aspects of Standardisation

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Standards are technical specifications that provide rules for products, services, processes, etc. How a toy should be manufactured to be safe, the height of a chair to feel comfortable, the process of protecting a

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computer system from cyber-attacks and many others. Similarly, legislation also provides rules to be followed on a very broad range of topics, and sometimes overlapping topics. Standards and the law often have a complementary relationship: without standards, a law on product safety is too vague; without the law, standards in specific areas do not have the same outreach and success. Sometimes, the relationship between standards and the law is mere co-existence: standards may provide rules on a topic that is of no interest to the legislator e.g., hydraulic turbines, and vice versa. However, the hierarchy between standards and the law is always clear: the rules provided for by a law supersede any conflicting rules provided for by a technical standard.

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3., S6.2., S6.6.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Good practice:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/legal-aspects-standardisation-relationship-standards-and-law-eu>

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › Blind, K. (2024): The role of the quality infrastructure within socio-technical transformations: A European perspective, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Volume 199, 123019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.123019>.
- › Degallaix, L., (2018). The Use of Standards in Legislation and Policies. How to ensure a legally sound and socially acceptable use of standards by policymakers in view of the CJEU James Elliott ruling and other court cases' ECOS.
- › Delimatsis, P. (2019). International trade law and technical standardisation. In J. Contreras (Ed.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Technical Standardisation Law: Further Intersections of Public and Private Law* (pp. 7-27). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316416785.002>.
- › Delimatsis, P. (2018). Global Standard-Setting 2.0: How the WTO Spotlights ISO and Impacts the Transnational Standard-Setting Process, *Duke Journal of Comparative & International Law*, 28, 273-326. <https://scholarship.law.duke.edu/djcil/vol28/iss2/3>
- › CEN CENELEC Guide 30, European Guide on Standards and Regulation – Better regulation through the use of voluntary standards - Guidance for policymakers.

- › European Commission, Falke, J., Schepel, H., Legal aspects of standardisation in the Member States of the EC and EFTA. Volume 1 – Comparative Report, Falke, J., Schepel, H., Publications Office, 2000.
- › Fontanelli, F. (2011). ISO and CODEX Standards and International Trade Law: What gets said is not what's heard. *The International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, 60, 4.
- › Gamito, M. C. (2024). The role of ETSI in the EU's regulation and governance of artificial intelligence. *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13511610.2024.2349627>.
- › Kamara, I. (2022). General Court EU: Commercial interests block the right to access European harmonized standards. *Journal of Standardisation*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.18757/jos.2022.6397>.
- › Kamara, I. (2024). European cybersecurity standardisation: a tale of two solitudes in view of Europe's cyber resilience. *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13511610.2024.2349626>.
- › Kamara, I. (2022). 'General Court EU: Commercial interests block the right to access European harmonized standards' *Journal of Standardisation*, Vol. 1, <https://doi.org/10.18757/jos.2022.6397>.
- › Kamara, I., (2017). Co-regulation in EU personal data protection: the case of technical standards and the privacy by design standardisation 'mandate', in *European Journal of Law and Technology*, Vol. 8, No. 1. <https://ejlt.org/index.php/ejlt/article/view/545/723>.
- › Kanevskaia, O. (2022). *The Law and Practice of Global ICT Standardisation*. Cambridge International Trade and Economic Law. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- › Schepel, H. (2015). Between standards and regulation: on the concept of 'de facto mandatory standards' after tuna ii and fra.bo. *Law, Economics and Politics of International Standardisation*, pp. 199-214.
- › Senden, L. (2017). The Constitutional Fit of European Standardisation Put to the Test. *Legal Issues of Economic Integration*, 44(4).
- › Verbruggen, P. (2018). Tort Liability for Standards Development in the United States and the European Union. *Forthcoming in J. Contreras (ed), Cambridge Handbook of Technical Standardisation Law*, 2.
- › van Leeuwen, B. (2013). From status to impact, and the role of national legislation: the application of article 34 tfeu to a private certification organization in fra.bo. *European Journal of Risk Regulation*, 4(3), 405–408. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1867299X00002713>.

11. SMEs and Standardisation

11.1. Topic: SMEs and Standardisation

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Compared to large enterprises, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are constantly struggling to compete on an equal footing and achieve sustained success in the global economy (Tosic & Mijatovic, 2021). The specificities of small enterprises have been extensively explored by the literature, thereby suggesting that the "ultimate power of control lies usually in the hands of owners or managers" (Wong & Aspinwall, 2004). Most owners or managers of SMEs "usually do not know how to delegate" or there are no qualified employees that are ready or eager to assume some of the authority and responsibility (see Haksever, 1996). This might be the reason why owners or managers of SMEs usually end up making most of the decisions, even the ones about areas, such as finance, operation, or knowledge management (KM) – "that are usually

the responsibility of an expert professional in large firms" (Haksever, 1996). Considering that owners or managers of SMEs often seem to be too busy with "fire-fighting – dealing with urgent tasks for the day-to-day survival of the enterprise" (Wong & Aspinwall, 2004) – it may be reasonable to expect that they will have little time to deal with standardisation, or any other strategic issue that may be relevant (De Vries et al., 2009). SMEs usually have "a short-term view of their business" which is why they may see standards "as a necessary evil" and not "the powerful tool to achieve their business objectives" (Stroyan & Brown, 2012). Without a clear standardisation-policy and an organizational structure to fulfil this policy, standardisation will not yield results (Slob & De Vries, 2002). The same authors argue that company standardisation can be seen as a form of KM, where tacit knowledge is being transformed into explicit knowledge (Slob & De Vries, 2002). The external world usually burdens SMEs "to show the depth of their expertise and ability to manage such expertise" (Desouza & Awazu, 2006). Assuming that owners and managers of SMEs must have had some level of expertise that enabled them to start their business activities in the first place (and carry them forward), given their lack of resources or capabilities, it might not be expertise in standardisation (Tosic & Mijatovic, 2021). Due to the mostly negative perception of standards/standardisation, SMEs are more likely to use the services of consultants as the fastest and the easiest solution that is available on the market (Mijatović et al., 2019). SMEs simply do not have the time, competent employees, or money to get involved in standards development, ... they evaluate the time spent on creating standards as too long, and they face higher costs (compared to their larger counterparts) of getting involved in technical committees (De Vries et al., 2009). Contrary to the conventional thinking that formal education about standardisation (alone) shall be enough for acquiring knowledge, skills, competencies, and experience in standardisation matters – when it comes to the small business community – the focus shall unanimously be on lifelong learning (Tosic & Mijatovic, 2021).

The ILOs examples: TBD

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Good practice:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Recommended sources:

- › Abdelkafi, N., Bekkers, R., Bolla, R., Rodriguez-Ascaso, A., & Wetterwald, M. (2021). Understanding ICT Standardisation: Principles and Practice, ETSI 2021, URL: https://www.etsi.org/images/files/Education/Textbook_Understanding_ICT_Standardisation.pdf, 2nd Edition, Chapter 6.
- › Blind, K., Mangelsdorf, A. (2016): Motives to standardize: Empirical evidence from Germany. *Technovation*, 48-49, 13–24.

- › De Vries, H. J., Blind, K., Mangelsdorf, A., Verheul, H., & Zwan, J. van der. (2009). SME access to European standardisation: Enabling small and medium-sized enterprises to achieve greater benefit from standards and from involvement in standardisation.
- › Mazzarol, T., & Redboud, S. (2020). Small Business Management Development: Theory and Practice. In Springer Texts in Business and Economics (4th ed.). Springer Nature Singapore Pte Ltd.
- › Mijatović, I. (2014). The Need for Standardisation in SMEs Networks. *Management - Journal for Theory and Practice of Management*, 19(73), 35–40.
- › Mijatović, I., Tošić, B., & Jovanović, M. (2019). The acquiring of the knowledge about standards in the digital era. *Amfiteatru Economic*, 21(51), 427–441. <https://doi.org/10.24818/EA/2019/51/427>.
- › Tošić, B., & Mijatović, I. (2021). Education about standardisation as the foundation for the expertise development of SMEs. *Tehnika*, 76(4), 521–528.

12. Quality Infrastructure (QI)

12.1. Topic: Quality Infrastructure (QI)

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The members of the International Network on Quality Infrastructure (INetQI) have recently agreed upon the definition of Quality Infrastructure (QI) as "the system comprising the organizations (public and private), together with the policies, relevant legal and regulatory framework, and practices needed to support and enhance the quality, safety and environmental soundness of goods, services, and processes" (InetQI, 2024). QI relies on metrology, standardisation, accreditation, conformity assessment, and market surveillance (InetQI, 2024). National Quality Infrastructure (NQI) is a system which consists of three core components without which its other parts cannot operate optimally: metrology, standardisation, and accreditation and services based on these components consist of calibration (derived from metrology), testing, inspection, and certification that are enhanced by market surveillance (the government's feedback and control mechanism) (Kellerman, 2019, pp. 42).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3., S6.2., S6.6., S7.1., S7.2., S7.10.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Good practice:

Educators teaching about QI usually do so by focusing on the essential components of both QI and NQI: (1) metrology, (2) standardisation, (3) accreditation, (4) conformity assessment, and (5) market surveillance. Educators usually emphasize how each essential component supports economic development, ensures quality and safety, and facilitates international trade by building trust in products and services. Educators use interactive workshops to demonstrate the relationship among the essential components of QI, e.g., how

metrology underpins testing and calibration, or how accreditation validates the competence of conformity assessment bodies. They also use case studies to demonstrate the real-world application of QI, e.g., how NQI supports international trade agreements and/or enhances the competitiveness of SMEs.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/quality-infrastructure>

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › Blind, K. (2024): The role of the quality infrastructure within socio-technical transformations: A European perspective, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Volume 199, 123019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.123019>.
- › InetQI. (2022). Quality Infrastructure. Accessed on November 09, 2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.inetqi.net/documentation/quality-infrastructure-definition/>.
- › Kellerman, M. (2019). Ensuring Quality to Gain Access to Global Markets (A Reform Toolkit). Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from: <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/249621553265195570-0090022019/original/FullQIToolkitReport.pdf>.
- › The World Bank. (2018). Quality Infrastructure. Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/competitiveness/brief/qi>.

12.2. Topic: The Role of Metrology in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Metrology is the oldest of three core components of QI and thus it has become one of the most sophisticated sciences and one in which cooperation across the world is essential to maintaining modern technology (Kellerman, 2019). QI relies on a national measurement system that ensures that measurements are made with appropriate accuracy and reliability and may be related to other measurements made domestically or internationally (ISO/UNIDO, 2010). Measurement also underpins testing as many items require calibration by specialist laboratories to ensure that such tests are traceable to international measurement standards (ISO/UNIDO, 2010). Manufacturing also requires consistent and reliable measurements for the interoperability and compatibility of components, as do measurements associated with traded commodities (ISO/UNIDO, 2010). At the international level, the measurement science and measurement capabilities are coordinated by the International Bureau of Weights and Measures (BIPM) (see more at ISO/UNIDO, 2010). The BIPM is an intergovernmental organization established by the Meter Convention through which Member States act together on matters related to measurement science and measurement standards (BIPM, 2024). At the regional level, the collaboration among National Measurement Institutes (NMIs) is coordinated by Regional Metrology Organizations (RMOs) (Howarth & Redgrave, 2008). At the national level, NMIs are responsible for providing the compatibility of measurements (ISO/UNIDO, 2010). It is their responsibility to provide the measurement capabilities needed within their economies and maintain capabilities which provide comparability with other economies

(ISO/UNIDO, 2010). Still, within many economies, access to appropriate high-level measurements for some quantities must be through NMIs from other economies (ISO/UNIDO, 2010).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3., S6.2., S6.6., S7.1, S7.2., S7.10.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. EURAMET. (2008). Metrology - In Short, Third Edition, Chapter 4, Measurement's impact: Some examples, pp. 48-58.

The link: https://www.euramet.org/securedl/sdl-eyJ0eXAiOiJKV1QiLCJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiJ9.eyJpYXQiOiJlE3MzAyNzY2NTAsImV4cCI6MTc2MTg5OTA1MCwidXNlcil6MCwiZ3JvdXBzIjpbMCwtMV0sImZpbGUiOiJNZWRpYS9kb2NzL1B1YmxpY2F0aW9ucy9NZXRyb2xvZ3lfaW5fc2hvcnRfM3JkX2VkLnBkZiIsInBhZ2UiOiJQ1NX0.1V6jJeVWS99jQLZO6y-nS8_DaxwCVUvZdKhwy-13GX8/Metrology in short 3rd ed.pdf

Good practice:

Educators teaching about metrology usually focus on its critical role in ensuring accuracy and reliability across industries. They usually start with foundational concepts, such as the Meter Convention and the SI system, thus emphasizing its significance for consistency in manufacturing, scientific research, and global trade. Additionally, they emphasize the role of NMIs (e.g., Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) in Germany) and international agreements, such as the Meter Convention in harmonizing measurements all around the world. Finally, they may also choose to demonstrate some measurement techniques or even calibration certificates, thereby establishing the relationship between theoretical knowledge and practical skills and competencies. Through lessons, students acquire knowledge of how metrology underpins innovation, ensures compliance with standards, and ensures trust which is seen as crucial for everyday life and global commerce.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://www.hsbooster.eu/training-academy/role-metrology-quality-infrastructure>

Other sources on Metrology:

- › Bucher, J., et al. (2004). The Metrology Handbook. The Measurement Quality Division, ASQ Quality Press.
- › Erard, L. et al. (2006). Organization of Metrology: Industrial, Scientific, Legal. In D., Placko (Ed.). Metrology in industry - The Key for Quality (1st ed.). London: ISTE Ltd.
- › Howarth, P., Redgrave, F. (2008). Metrology – In Short (EURAMET, 3rd ed.),
- › Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.euramet.org/publications-media-centre/documents/metrology-in-short/tiL=0>.

- › ISO/UNIDO. (2010). Building trust. The Conformity Assessment Toolbox. Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from:
https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/archive/pdf/en/casco_building-trust.pdf.
- › Kellerman, M. (2019). Ensuring Quality to Gain Access to Global Markets (A Reform Toolkit). Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from:
<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/249621553265195570-0090022019/original/FullQIToolkitReport.pdf>.

Other sources on Metrology Standards:

- › Allen, R. A., Cresswell, M. W., Murabito, C. E., Dixson, R. G., & Bogardus, E. H. (2003). Critical dimension calibration standards for ULSI metrology. In AIP Conference Proceedings (Vol. 683, No. 1, pp. 421-428). American Institute of Physics.
- › Guan, Y., & Tortonesi, M. (2004). Metrology standards for semiconductor manufacturing. In Proceedings. 7th International Conference on Solid-State and Integrated Circuits Technology, 2004. (Vol. 1, pp. 588-593). IEEE.
- › Kovalevsky, J. (2000). The consequences of the mutual recognition of measurement standards for international metrology. *Accreditation and quality assurance*, 5(10), 409-413.
- › Marschall, S., Schedrick, N., & Hahlweg, C. F. (2018, September). Standard specifications vs metrology of LED illumination systems. In *Novel Optical Systems Design and Optimization XXI* (Vol. 10746, pp. 65-73). SPIE.
- › Miles, J. (2009). 16. Metrology and standards for nanotechnology. *New global frontiers in regulation: The age of nanotechnology*, 333.
- › Monteiro, E. C., & Leon, L. F. (2015). Metrological reliability of medical devices. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 588, No. 1, p. 012032). IOP Publishing.
- › Postek, M. T., & Lyons, K. (2007). Instrumentation, metrology, and standards: Key elements for the future of nanomanufacturing. In *Instrumentation, Metrology, and Standards for Nanomanufacturing* (Vol. 6648, pp. 11-17). SPIE.
- › Rychlik, M., Zappa, G., Añorga, L., Belc, N., Castanheira, I., Donard, O. F., ... & Zoani, C. (2018). Ensuring food integrity by metrology and FAIR data principles. *Frontiers in chemistry*, 06/49.
- › Sharma, C., Mandal, T. K., Singh, S., Gupta, G., Kulshrestha, M. J., Johri, P., ... & Kumar, M. (2020). Metrology for Atmospheric Environment: Part II: Environmental Governance. *Metrology for Inclusive Growth of India*, 691-729.
- › Swann, G.M.P. (2009): *The Economics of Metrology and Measurement; Report for National Measurement Office, Department for Business, Innovation and Skills.*
- › Williams, R. L., Team, P., & Staff, U. S. P. (2006). Official USP Reference Standards: Metrology concepts, overview, and Scientific Issues and Opportunities. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, Vol. 40(1), pp. 03-15.

12.3. Topic: The Role of Standardisation in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The World Trade Organization's Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade (WTO/TBT) was established to ensure that technical regulations, standards and specifications required to assess conformity with them, do

not create unnecessary obstacles to international trade (ISO/UNIDO, 2010). Successive reviews of the WTO/TBT Agreement have noted the usefulness of ISO/IEC conformity assessment standards and guides in harmonizing conformity assessment activities and as benchmarks for the technical competence of conformity assessment bodies so that adequate credibility and confidence in the obtained results may be achieved (ISO/UNIDO, 2010). The use of ISO/IEC conformity assessment standards helps to overcome trade barriers and promotes the international recognition of conformity assessment activities, market surveillance, and other related activities, as well as enables the worldwide acceptance of the results of these activities (ISO/UNIDO, 2010).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3., S6.2., S6.6., S7.1., S7.2., S7.10.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Good practice:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://www.hsbooster.eu/training-academy/role-standardisation-quality-infrastructure>

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › Howarth, P., Redgrave, F. (2008). Metrology – In Short (EURAMET, 3rd ed.), Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.euramet.org/publications-media-centre/documents/metrology-in-short/tiL=0>.
- › ISO/UNIDO. (2010). Building trust. The Conformity Assessment Toolbox. Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from: https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/archive/pdf/en/casco_building-trust.pdf.
- › Kellerman, M. (2019). Ensuring Quality to Gain Access to Global Markets (A Reform Toolkit). Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from: <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/249621553265195570-0090022019/original/FullQIToolkitReport.pdf>.

12.4. Topic: The Role of Accreditation in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

According to the ISO 17000:2020, Conformity Assessment – Vocabulary and general principles, accreditation is defined as "a third-party attestation related to a conformity assessment body, conveying formal demonstration of its competence, impartiality, and consistent operation in performing specific conformity assessment activities" (ISO/IEC, 2020). Accordingly, "accreditation as such is applicable in the case of

laboratories, inspection bodies, certification bodies, validation and verification bodies, and bodies that certify personnel" (Kellerman, 2019). Additionally, the use of the ISO/IEC 17000 standards series developed by international organizations for standardisation ISO/IEC has recently become imperative, but sometimes national standards (not harmonized with the ISO/IEC 17000 standards series) are also used in some countries (Kellerman, 2019). At the international level, two key international organizations for accreditation are the International Laboratory Accreditation Cooperation (ILAC) and the International Accreditation Forum (IAF) both having the aim of facilitating international trade through enhanced confidence (see ISO/UNIDO, 2010). At the regional level, Regional Accreditation Bodies (RABs) are the ones that provide accreditation services to smaller countries in a region established by a trade agreement – have been established in some regions and have been paid special attention through ILAC and the IAF, such as Southern African Development Community Accreditation Services (SADCAS) (ISO/UNIDO, 2010). At the national level, member states may establish National Accreditation Focal Points (NAFPs) to be liaison mechanisms between the RAB and entities wishing to be accredited (ISO/UNIDO, 2010). NAFPs may be established within a ministry or the national standards body (if there is no potential conflict of interest). As most developing countries still do not have the resources and capabilities to establish a single NAB, one of the major decisions for a developing country involves the way in which the conformity assessment activities (and the accreditation requirements) are to be carried out (ISO/UNIDO, 2010).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3., S6.2., S6.6., S7.1., S7.2., S7.10.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Good practice:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://www.hsbooster.eu/training-academy/role-accreditation-quality-infrastructure>

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › Blind, K., Mangelsdorf, A., & Pohlisch, J. (2018). The effects of cooperation in accreditation on international trade: Empirical evidence on ISO 9000 certifications. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 198, 50-59.

- › Howarth, P., Redgrave, F. (2008). Metrology – In Short (EURAMET, 3rd ed.), Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from: <https://www.euramet.org/publications-media-centre/documents/metrology-in-short/tiL=0>.
- › ISO/UNIDO. (2010). Building trust. The Conformity Assessment Toolbox. Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from: https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/archive/pdf/en/casco_building-trust.pdf.
- › Kellerman, M. (2019). Ensuring Quality to Gain Access to Global Markets (A Reform Toolkit). Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from: <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/249621553265195570-0090022019/original/FullQIToolkitReport.pdf>.

12.5. Topic: The Role of Conformity Assessment in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

According to ISO 17000:2020, Conformity Assessment: Vocabulary and General Principles, conformity assessment is defined as "a demonstration that specified requirements are fulfilled" (ISO/IEC, 2020). Additionally, the object of conformity assessment is defined as "an entity to which these specified requirements apply (e.g., product, process, service, system, installation, project, data, design, material, claim, person, body or organization, or any combination thereof)" (ISO/IEC, 2020). Similarly, the first-party conformity assessment activity is "conformity assessment activity that is performed by the person or organization that provides or that is the object of conformity assessment (e.g., activities performed by providers, designers or owners of the object, investors in the object, and advertisers or promoters of the object)", the second-party conformity assessment activity is "conformity assessment activity that is performed by a person or organization that has a user interest in the object of conformity assessment (e.g., purchasers or users of products, or potential customers seeking to rely on a supplier's management system, or organizations representing those interests, such as consumer advocacy organizations, regulators implementing legislation governing products and services for the protection of consumer and public interests, centralized government procurement organizations and private sector purchasing agents", and the third-party conformity assessment activity is "conformity assessment activity that is performed by a person or organization that is independent of the provider of the object of conformity assessment and has no user interest in the object of conformity assessment" (ISO/IEC, 2020). Additionally, the conformity assessment system is defined as "a set of rules and procedures for the management of similar or related conformity assessment schemes" and the conformity assessment scheme is defined as "a set of rules and procedures that describes the objects of conformity assessment, identifies the specified requirements, and provides the methodology for performing conformity assessment activity" (ISO/IEC, 2020). Generally speaking, conformity assessment activities comprise testing, inspection, and certification "used in all fields of investigation, innovation, process improvement, productivity, product development, or compliance" (see Kellerman, 2019).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3., S6.2., S6.6., S7.1., S7.2., S7.10.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

1. IEC/ISO/UNIDO. (2022). Building Trust: The Conformity Assessment Toolbox. Chapter 6., Case studies, pp. 156-166. The link:
https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/archive/pdf/en/casco_building-trust.pdf

Good practice:

Educators teaching about the role of conformity assessment in quality infrastructure usually focus on its key role in verifying that products, services, or systems meet specified standards and regulatory requirements. They explore conformity assessment processes, including testing, calibration, inspection, and certification, explaining the significance of conformity assessment processes in ensuring quality, safety, and market access. Educators may also want to offer a complete understanding of conformity assessment schemes and systems. Educators often use case studies and examples of conformity assessment processes from various industries.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://www.hsbooster.eu/training-academy/role-conformity-assessment-quality-infrastructure>

If you want to teach about conformity assessment schemes/systems, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/conformity-assessment-schemes-and-systems>

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › ISO/IEC. (2020). Conformity assessment — Vocabulary and general principles.
- › ISO/UNIDO. (2010). Building trust. The Conformity Assessment Toolbox. Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from:
https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/archive/pdf/en/casco_building-trust.pdf.
- › Kellerman, M. (2019). Ensuring Quality to Gain Access to Global Markets (A Reform Toolkit). Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from:
<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/249621553265195570-0090022019/original/FullQIToolkitReport.pdf>.
- › Stuurman, K., & Lachaud, E. (2022). Regulating AI. A label to complete the proposed Act on Artificial Intelligence. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 44, 105657.

12.6. Topic: The Role of Market Surveillance in the Quality Infrastructure (QI)

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

Market surveillance shall be seen as a continuous evolution of conformity assessment activities as a basis for maintaining the validity of the statement or the mark of conformity (ISO/UNIDO, 2010). To ensure that market surveillance activities are carried out adequately, most countries establish regulatory authorities to carry out market surveillance (Kellerman, 2019). Some countries will establish one or more regulatory

authorities with specific mandates within each ministry and some countries will establish only four or five larger regulatory authorities within sectors (e.g., telecommunication services, transportation, building and construction, etc.) (Kellerman, 2019). Small countries may sometimes consider establishing one regional regulatory authority for all products falling within the scope of technical regulations and market surveillance (Kellerman, 2019). Although surveillance activities should be conducted regularly, economic constraints usually lead to targeted surveillance where risks are likely to be higher and non-compliances are likely to be more common (ISO/UNIDO, 2010). For market surveillance activities to be efficient, regulatory authorities should be equipped with the necessary resources and responsibilities to conduct market surveillance activities (Kellerman, 2019).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3., S6.2., S6.6., S7.1., S7.2., S7.10.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

- › Example: Market Surveillance in the EU

The link: https://commission.europa.eu/business-economy-euro/product-safety-and-requirements/product-safety/product-safety-and-market-surveillance_en

Good practice:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://www.hsbooster.eu/training-academy/role-market-surveillance-quality-infrastructure>

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › EC. (2022). The 'Blue Guide' on the implementation of EU product rules 2022
- › (Text with EEA relevance) (2022/C 247/01). Official Journal of the European Union, vol. 65. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/tiuri=OJ:C:2022:247:FULL&from=EN>.
- › EU. (2019). Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 of the European Parliament and of the Council on market surveillance and compliance of products. Accessed on January 23, 2023. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/tiuri=CELEX:32019R1020>.
- › ISO. (2012). A Guide to Good Practice: Principles and Practices in Product Regulation and Market Surveillance. Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from: https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/archive/pdf/en/casco_guide.pdf.

- › ISO/UNIDO. (2010). Building trust. The Conformity Assessment Toolbox. Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from:
https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/archive/pdf/en/casco_building-trust.pdf.
- › Kellerman, M. (2019). Ensuring Quality to Gain Access to Global Markets (A Reform Toolkit). Accessed on October 27, 2022. Retrieved from:
<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/249621553265195570-0090022019/original/FullQIToolkitReport.pdf>.

13. European Values & Principles and Standardisation

13.1. Topic:

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The ILOs examples: **TBD**

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Good practice:

Recommended sources:

14. Roles of Standardisation in Digital and Green Transformation

14.1. Topic:

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The ILOs examples: **TBD**

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Good practice:

Recommended sources:

KA3. Strategic Use of Standards

15. Motives for and barriers to applying standards (specific)

15.1. Topic: Motives for and barriers to applying standards

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.2., K7.1.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Good practice:

Recommended sources

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › Blind, K., Filipović, E., & Lazina, L. K. (2022). Motives to Publish, Patent and to Standardize: An Explorative Study Based on Individual Engineers' Assessments. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 175(September 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121420>.
- › Blind, K., Lorenz, A., & Rauber, J. (2021). Drivers for Companies' Entry into Standard-Setting Organizations. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 68(1), 33–44. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2020.2975427>.
- › Blind, K., & Mangelsdorf, A. (2016). Motives to standardize: Empirical evidence from Germany. *Technovation*, 48–49, 13–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2016.01.001>.
- › de Vries, H. J., Blind, K., Mangelsdorf, A., Verheul, H., & Zwan, J. van der. (2009). SME access to European standardisation: Enabling small and medium-sized enterprises to achieve greater benefit from standards and from involvement in standardisation.
- › Riillo, C. A. F. (2013). Profiles and motivations of standardisation players. *International Journal of Standards and Standardisation Research*, 11(2), 17–33. <https://doi.org/10.4018/jitsr.2013070102>.

16. How to find the right standard?

16.1. Topic: How to find the right standard?

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important

There are many resources created by formal organizations for standardisation, professional and industrial associations, business associations, consortia, and fora to assist customers and users to address and find the right standard(s). Some of these organizations offer their standards freely via their website (e.g., standards developed by the ITU-T are publicly available and can be accessed freely) and some of them offer standards for a fee (e.g., most international, regional, or national SDOs). For example, one of the world's largest bibliographic databases of national, European, and international standards developed by over 200 organizations for standardisation from 29 countries, with 2,400,000 records is called the Perinorm database. (The Perinorm database for searching and managing standards has been discontinued as of December 31, 2022.). New and innovative solutions, based on the newest technologies, have been developed by the members of the Consortium that created the Perinorm database. You may find these solutions at the links: <https://www.beuth.de/de/normen-management> and <https://cdn.afnor.org/com/cobaz/discover-en.html>.

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.2., K7.1.

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Good practice:

Recommended sources

If you would like to teach students how to find the right standard, the practical instructions can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/how-find-right-standard>

KA4. Strategic Participation in Standards Development

17. Motives for and barriers to participating in standards development

17.1. Topic: Motives for and barriers to participating in standards development

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.2., K7.1.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Good practice:

Recommended sources

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › Blind, K., Filipović, E., & Lazina, L. K. (2022). Motives to Publish, Patent and to Standardize: An Explorative Study Based on Individual Engineers' Assessments. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 175(September 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121420>.
- › Blind, K., Lorenz, A., & Rauber, J. (2021). Drivers for Companies' Entry into Standard-Setting Organizations. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 68(1), 33–44. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2020.2975427>.
- › Blind, K., & Mangelsdorf, A. (2016). Motives to standardize: Empirical evidence from Germany. *Technovation*, 48–49, 13–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2016.01.001>.
- › de Vries, H. J., Blind, K., Mangelsdorf, A., Verheul, H., & Zwan, J. van der. (2009). SME access to European standardisation: Enabling small and medium-sized enterprises to achieve greater benefit from standards and from involvement in standardisation.
- › Riillo, C. A. F. (2013). Profiles and motivations of standardisation players. *International Journal of IT Standards and Standardisation Research*, 11(2), 17–33. <https://doi.org/10.4018/jitsr.2013070102>.

18. How to participate in Technical Committees (TCs) and Working Groups (WGs)?

18.1. Topic: How to participate in Technical Committees (TCs) and Working Groups (WGs)?

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

ISO aims to bring together members from 167 different countries to develop voluntary, consensus-based, international standards while also contributing significantly to sustainable development (ISO, 2022a). NSBs can become ISO members and there can be only one member per country (ISO, 2022b). There are three member categories: full members, correspondent members, and subscriber members, and each category enjoys different benefits (ISO, 2022b). The Committee Manager deals with the administrative tasks of the committee and must remain neutral when dealing with members of the committee (ISO, 2020a). The Committee Chair deals with the managerial tasks and works with the Committee Manager (ISO, 2020b). The Liaison may be established between ISO committees, between ISO committees and IEC committees, and between ISO committees and external organizations (ISO, 2020c). The Liaison is responsible for maintaining the relationship between stakeholders, enabling their voices to be heard throughout standards development (ISO, 2020c). There are many resources created by the ISO Central Secretariat aimed at assisting Committee Managers, Committee Chairs, and Committee Liaisons. The WGs established by TCs, SCs, or PCs are managed by the Convenors who lead the WG towards achieving the goals for which the WG was originally established (ISO, 2019d). Convenors are appointed for three years and can be reappointed an unlimited number of times (ISO, 2019d). Only experts elected by the members who have become P-members (and category A liaisons) can become members of the WGs (ISO, 2019d). Members may choose to become O-members or P-members (ISO, 2022c).

The ILOs examples: K6.1., K6.2., K6.3., K7.1., K7.2., K7.3, and S6.6. toward S7.6. and S7.11.

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Good practice:

Still looking for adequate recommendations for this chapter at the time of finishing this version of document D 2.3.

Recommended sources:

If you are new to the topic, the basics can be found at:

- › <https://hsbooster.eu/training-academy/how-participate-tcs-or-wgs>

Other sources relevant to the topic:

- › ISO. (2020). Getting Started Toolkit: For Committee Liaisons.

- › Accessed on November 05, 2022. Retrieved from:
https://isotc.iso.org/livelink/livelink/fetch/2000/2122/15507012/20090199/Getting_started_committee_liaisons.pdf?nodeid=21124173&vernum=-2&objid=15508281&vernum=-2.
- › ISO. (2020). Getting Started Toolkit: For ISO Committee Chairs. Accessed on November 05, 2022. Retrieved from:
https://isotc.iso.org/livelink/livelink/fetch/2000/2122/15507012/20090199/Getting_started_Chairs.pdf?nodeid=17891748&vernum=-2.
- › ISO. (2020). Getting Started Toolkit: For ISO Committee Managers. Accessed on November 05, 2022. Retrieved from:
https://isotc.iso.org/livelink/livelink/fetch/2000/2122/15507012/20090199/Getting_started_Committee_Managers.pdf?nodeid=17891748&vernum=-2.
- › ISO. (2010). Guidance for ISO Liaison Organizations: Engaging Stakeholders and Building Consensus. Accessed on November 05, 2022. Retrieved from:
https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/archive/pdf/en/guidance_liaison-organizations.pdf.
- › ISO. (2020). My ISO job – What delegates and experts need to know. Accessed on January 26, 2023. Retrieved from:
<https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/store/en/PUB100037.pdf>.
- › ISO/IEC. (2022). ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1, Consolidated ISO Supplement, Procedure for the technical work – Procedures specific to ISO, Thirteenth edition, 2022, Accessed on January 26, 2023. Retrieved from:
<https://isotc.iso.org/livelink/livelink?func=ll&objId=4230452&objAction=browse&sort=subtype>.
- › ISO/IEC. (2021). ISO/IEC Directives, Part 2, Principles and rules for the structure and Drafting of ISO and IEC documents. Accessed on January 26, 2023. Retrieved from:
<https://isotc.iso.org/livelink/livelink?func=ll&objId=4230456&objAction=browse&sort=subtype>.

19. How to identify the need for a new standard or improvement of an existing one?

19.1. Topic: How to identify the need for a new standard or improvement of an existing one?

Short instruction /Why the understanding of this topic is important:

The ILOs examples: TBD

Recommended duration of tutorials: from 30 minutes to 90 minutes

Recommended Teaching Case studies/Serious Games/Other:

Good practice:

Recommended sources:

Appendix 2. The ILOs Framework for Standardisation Education

Note: The general value-based ILOs framework for standardisation education is given in Table 5 of D2.1.

Levels		Knowledge	Examples of skills	Responsibility and autonomy
Level 0	Early childhood education (age 0/3 to 3/6)	<p>The learner is expected to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K0.1: know that standards are similar to guidelines and rules and that they make sure that things work safely and consistently • K0.2: understand the importance of having and following standards, rule, guidelines to make sure that things are understandable for all • K0.3: understand simple examples of standardised products and services such as electricity, traffic lights colours, emergency and rescue services (police, ambulance, fire brigade) etc. • K0.4: form a sense of right and wrong 	<p>The learner is able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S0.1: follow simple rules and routines • S0.2: role-play situations of rule-following and point at the rules that are followed • S0.3: in an interactive game or activity discuss with the group examples of simple standardised products or services from everyday life and why they are important 	<p>The learner can engage in simple play and creative activities with guidance and under direct supervision in a structured context.</p>

<p>Level 1</p>	<p>Primary education (age 5/7 to 10/12)</p>	<p>The learner is expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K1.1: to have a basic general knowledge of standards and standardisation • K1.2: to have a basic general knowledge of values in standardisation 	<p>The learner is able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S1.1: define the concept of standards and standardisation by using examples • S1.2: outline the purpose of standards and standardisation (to ensure consistency, safety, understandability) and the benefits of having standardised products, services and processes in general • S1.3: list simple examples of standardised products, services and processes and recognise what values they support (ex. traffic signs & values such as safety, or transparency) • S1.4: list values and outline examples of standardised products, services and processes that they support 	<p>The learner can perform basic tasks under direct supervision in a structured context. They can participate in and contribute to group activities.</p>
<p>Level 2</p>	<p>Lower secondary education (age 10/13 to 14/16)</p>	<p>The learner is expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K2.1: to have a basic factual knowledge of standardisation • K2.2: to have a basic factual knowledge of values in standardisation <p>K2.3: to have basic knowledge of legal, ethical, environmental and gender aspects related to standardisation</p>	<p>The learner is able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S2.1: explain the basic concepts in the field of standardisation • S2.2: name and describe few existing standards • S2.3: clarify why concrete standards are important • S2.4: give examples of important milestones in the history of standardisation • S2.5: understand the concept of value • S2.6: compare simple standards to one another and the values they promote • S2.7: explain ideas and concepts of values relevant for a concrete standardisation case 	<p>The learner can study under supervision with some autonomy, for example, in carrying out their tasks, doing homework, planning the learning process. They can contribute to group activities.</p>

<p>Level 3</p>	<p>Upper secondary education (age 14/16 to 17/18)</p>	<p>The learner is expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K3.1: to have knowledge of facts, principles, processes, general concepts and players regarding standardisation • K3.2: to have knowledge of facts, principles, processes, general concepts and players related to values in standardisation • K3.3: to have knowledge of the legal, ethical, environmental and gender aspects related to standardisation 	<p>The learner is able to:</p> <p>Deliverable D2.3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3.1: explain more complex concepts used in standards and standardisation • S3.2: sketch the standardisation process (standards- development) at a glance • S3.3: analyse the standards ecosystem • S3.4: compare the SDOs in terms of scope, geographical focus, decision-making processes, standards development processes, structure, types of standards etc. • S3.5: explore the difference between various types of standards • S3.6: develop a deeper understanding of the history of standardisation • S3.7: explore the benefits and risks of standardisation • S3.8: integrate green/digital/gender considerations to existing standards use cases • S3.9: apply value-based concepts, terms and content to different industry-relevant or sector-specific contexts, scenarios 	<p>The learner can take responsibility for completion of tasks and for their learning process. They can participate in group projects meaningfully.</p>
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<p>Level 4</p>	<p>Post-secondary non-tertiary education (ca. age 18-20)</p>	<p>The learner is expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K4.1: to have a factual and theoretical knowledge in broad contexts regarding standardisation • K4.2: to have a factual and theoretical knowledge in broad contexts of values in standardisation <p>K4.3: to have factual and theoretical knowledge of the legal, ethical, environmental and gender aspects related to standardisation</p>	<p>The learner is able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S4.1: explain the functions of standardisation institutions and their processes • S4.2: select appropriate standardisation organisations • S4.3: search for and select appropriate standards for different scenarios and contexts • S4.4: determine which form of standardisation (formal vs. informal) is appropriate • S4.5: explain the impact of implementing standards • S4.6: analyse, interpret and evaluate values in different standardisation scenarios and (industry) sectors <p>S4.7: identify strategies to ensure more value-based approach in standardisation processes</p>	<p>Deliverable D2.3</p> <p>The learner can take responsibility for planning and managing their learning process. At the same time, they can participate actively in collaborative projects by providing meaningful contribution.</p>
<p>Level 5</p>	<p>Short-cycle tertiary education</p>	<p>The learner is expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K5.1: to have comprehensive, specialised, factual and theoretical knowledge of standardisation within one's field and an awareness of the boundaries of that knowledge • K5.2: to have comprehensive, specialised, factual and theoretical knowledge of values in standardisation within one's field and an awareness of the boundaries of that knowledge <p>K5.3: to have comprehensive, specialised, factual and theoretical knowledge of the legal, ethical, environmental and gender</p>	<p>The learner is able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S5.1: assess the need for standards • S5.2: assess the need for getting involved in standardisation • S5.3: propose new work items in standardisation • S5.4: explain the steps needed to identify and use standards relevant to a specific topic of interest • S5.5: analyse the interactions between standards and the regulatory framework • S5.6: outline the professional activities of a standardisation expert during committee meetings, between organisation meetings, inside his/her 	<p>The learner can manage and organise their learning process with very limited supervision. They can participate in collaborative group projects, make decisions, proposing steps and solutions.</p>

		<p>aspects related to standardisation within one's field</p>	<p>own organisation, further activities as a national delegate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S5.7: be passively involved in standardisation processes (observer) • S5.8: implement standards in product or process development • S5.9: reflect on possible (positive and negative) relations between the values relevant to a standardisation case <p>S5.10: carry out analysis of the value relations</p>	
<p>Level 6</p>	<p>Bachelor's level</p>	<p>The learner is expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K6.1: to have advanced knowledge of standards and standardisation within one's field, involving a critical understanding of theories and principles • K6.2: to have advanced knowledge of values in standards and standardisation within one's field, involving a critical understanding of theories and principles <p>K6.3: to have advanced knowledge of the legal, ethical, environmental and gender aspects related to standardisation within one's field</p>	<p>The learner is able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S6.1: be actively involved in standardisation processes (participant) • S6.2: illustrate the interactions between standards and the regulatory framework • S6.3: carry out deeper analysis of the value relations • S6.4: determine and analyse value conflicts in a standardisation use case • S6.5: propose solutions on simple value conflicts <p>S6.6: promote green/digital/gender aspects in standardisation through active participation in various initiatives</p>	<p>The learner can manage and organise their learning process autonomously and independently. They can participate in collaborative projects by carrying out more complex tasks and taking more responsibility for decision-making within the team.</p>

<p>Level 7</p>	<p>Master's level</p>	<p>The learner is expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K7.1: to have highly specialised knowledge, some of which is at the forefront of knowledge in standards and standardisation within one's field and at the interface between different fields, as the basis for original thinking and/or research • K7.2: to have highly specialised knowledge, some of which is at the forefront of knowledge of values in standards and standardisation within one's field and at the interface between different fields <p>K7.3: to have highly specialised knowledge of the legal, ethical, environmental and gender aspects related to standardisation within one's field and at the interface between different fields</p>	<p>The learner is able to:</p> <p>Deliverable D2.3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S7.1: evaluate existing policy documents on standardisation within one's field and at the interface between fields • S7.2: strategically influence the agenda in standardisation processes • S7.3: understand the key determinants of successful standardisation • S7.4: support the development of new more value- sensitive standards within their field • S7.5: influence the development of standardisation policies at national and international level • S7.6: lead standardisation committees • S7.7: depict the interdependencies between standardisation and innovation • S7.8: depict the relation between standardisation and IPR (relevance of patents, tension between patents and standards) • S7.9: propose solutions on more complex value conflicts in a standardisation use case • S7.10: understand standardisation in the context of the national quality infrastructure and the macroeconomic environment <p>S7.11: actively contribute to making standardisation processes and the standardisation working environment more respectful, inclusive, open and accessible</p>	<p>The learner can carry out tasks with high level of independence. They can mentor and guide others, take part in more complex collaborative projects, propose strategies.</p>
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<p>Level 8</p>	<p>Doctoral level</p>	<p>The learner is expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K8.1: to have knowledge on standards and standardisation at the most advanced theoretical level within one's field and at the interface between fields • K8.2: to have knowledge about values in standardisation at the most advanced theoretical level <p>K8.3: to have knowledge of the legal, ethical, environmental and gender aspects related to standardisation within one's field at the most advanced theoretical level</p>	<p>The learner is able to:</p> <p>Deliverable D2.3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S8.1: participate in discourse on standards and standardisation at the most advanced level • S8.2: critically evaluate existing policy documents on standardisation within one's field and at the interface between fields • S8.3: critically evaluate existing policy documents on values in standardisation within one's field and at the interface between fields • S8.4: propose solutions, new ideas, new work items and processes of standardisation within one's field and at the interface between fields • S8.5: write policy documents on standardisation • S8.6: reflect on European values and interests in standardisation on a meta-level • S8.7: conduct policy negotiations on values in standardisation in international settings <p>S8.8: lead complex projects on standardisation within one's field and at the interface between fields</p>	<p>The learner can carry out tasks independently. They can mentor and guide others, contribute to the development of new ideas or processes with minimal guidance.</p>
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